

MEMBERS CATALOGUE

2025

© European Network of Living Labs

This report is a compilation of activities
of the Network for the year 2025.

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For more than 15 years, ENoLL has stood as a community where trust, openness, innovation, and transparency guide everything we do. What began as a vision has grown into a global Network of over 500 certified members, and 184 active today: each one contributing unique strengths, and all benefitting from the collective value we create together.

Our Network is not a single entity, but a living ecosystem. Every member is rooted in their local community while remaining connected to fellow Living Labs worldwide. This interplay drives a continuous exchange of knowledge: bottom-up insights flowing from practice, and top-down dissemination of policies and proven approaches.

To safeguard excellence, we have established a rigorous certification process, ensuring that all members meet the demanding criteria of a Living Lab. This shared commitment to quality strengthens the Network as a whole, reinforcing both credibility and impact.

Looking ahead, our strategic ambition is clear: to expand opportunities, visibility, and value for our members, while confirming ENoLL's role as the world's leading actor in the Living Lab movement. The fact that more than 20% of our members now come from outside Europe is proof of our growing global relevance. A Network that grows is a Network that thrives, bringing richness, diversity, and opportunity to all.

At its heart, ENoLL embodies a simple but powerful principle: empower everyone to innovate!

Martina Desole
Director ENoLL

It is with great pleasure that I welcome you to discover the newest edition of the ENoLL Members' Catalogue.

This year marks another exciting milestone for our Network: we have grown to 184 members representing 41 countries. Our global reach has expanded even further, welcoming Czech Republic, India, Lithuania, and Kenya into the ENoLL community for the very first time. Each new country brings with it new perspectives, new expertise, and new opportunities to co-create the future together.

Within these pages, you will find the inspiring work of Living Labs from every corner of the world — each one dedicated to empowering people to innovate in their local contexts while contributing to global challenges. The diversity of our Members remains our greatest strength: interdisciplinary teams, open innovation practices, knowledge sharing, collaborative efforts, and a deep sense of social responsibility.

We encourage you to use this Catalogue as more than just a directory: let it be a gateway to meaningful connections. Identify potential partners, explore new collaborations, and imagine future projects together. Whether you are already part of our Network or considering joining, you are invited to engage with this vibrant international community dedicated to research, experimentation, sustainability, and impact.

ENoLL continues to grow, evolve, and thrive because of its Members — and we take immense pride in showcasing their remarkable contributions here. The true power of the Network is, indeed, the Network itself.

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What is ENoLL

The European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) is an international non-profit association headquartered in Brussels, Belgium, dedicated to advancing user-driven innovation ecosystems through the Living Lab approach. Established in 2006, ENoLL has grown into the only certification body and world's largest Living Lab network, bringing together over 480 historically recognised Living Labs to foster collaboration, experimentation, and co-creation that drive societal and economic impact. ENoLL facilitates knowledge exchange, supports joint initiatives, and promotes project partnerships among its members while advocating for the adoption of Living Lab methodologies globally.

Through its work, ENoLL influences public policy at both European and international levels, enabling the creation of innovative solutions that address societal challenges. More specifically, ENoLL supports its members in the **development of impactful, innovative products & services**, allowing them to expand their own value to their own stakeholders and beyond, facilitating knowledge exchange among members and externals.

ENoLL counts today **184 active members from 41 countries** located on five continents.

The governance and operations of ENoLL are organised through four key components:

- ENoLL Council
- ENoLL General Assembly
- ENoLL Office
- ENoLL Members

ENoLL Council

The Council, under the guidance of the Chairperson, serves as the executive body entrusted with defining the strategic orientations of the Association. These orientations are then implemented by the Secretariat and the Office. Composed of duly elected representatives of Members' organisations, the Council is responsible for supervising both the development and implementation of ENoLL's strategic objectives and operational activities. In fulfilling this role, it ensures coherence between long-term priorities and daily operations, thereby steering the network towards impactful and sustainable growth.

ENoLL General Assembly

The General Assembly constitutes the main decision-making body of ENoLL. It convenes all members of the association to deliberate and approve strategic decisions and initiatives. The GA ensures the representation of members in the network's priorities. Through its regular meetings and consultations, it upholds a forum for collective decision-making and reinforces the commitment of members to innovation and the exchange of knowledge.

ENoLL Office

The ENoLL Office acts as the operational arm of the association. Its primary role is to implement the decisions adopted by the General Assembly and the Council, while ensuring a proper and effective management of day-to-day activities of the network. The Office coordinates the execution of strategic initiatives, supports the development and delivery of projects, organises and manages events and capacity building activities, and facilitates communication and collaboration across the community of Members and with external relevant stakeholders. ENoLL Office is located at Avenue des Arts 6, 1210 Saint-Josse-ten-Noode, Brussels, Belgium.

What is a Living Lab

Living Labs are innovation environments where citizens, public authorities, private enterprises, and research institutions collaborate (Quadruple Helix model) to co-design, test, and validate new products, services, and systems. ENOLL empowers its members to apply this approach across diverse domains, such as health and wellbeing, soil-health, energy, mobility, agriculture, culture and creativity, social innovation, among others, fostering experimentation and the development of new business models.

A Living Lab can be setup and hosted by a university, city, research institute, municipality, or any organisation where the user is placed at the center of the innovation process.

In this context, Living Labs operate as intermediaries/orchestrators among citizens, government, industry and academia.

This catalogue presents ENOLL's global membership, highlighting organisations operating across diverse countries and representing a wide spectrum of thematic domains.

Living Labs are user-centred, open innovation ecosystems based on a systematic user co-creation approach, integrating research and innovation processes in real-life communities and settings.

ENoLL Working Groups (WGs)

ENoLL Working Groups are dynamic collaborative spaces within the ENoLL community designed to foster knowledge exchange, peer debate, and open innovation. WGs welcome both ENoLL Members and selected external stakeholders to collaborate on tackling pressing challenges and exploring emerging opportunities in key thematic areas.

With a long-term vision, ENoLL WGs foster inclusive cross-border and cross-sectoral collaboration. Through a variety of activities such as networking events, proposal writing, workshops, and virtual or in-person staff exchanges and visits, ENoLL Working Groups offer a platform for continuous learning and experience sharing.

Working Groups are open to Members as well as external stakeholders who wish to collaborate with experts in a specific domain. The focus areas of all Working Groups are briefly outlined below. More information at <https://enoll.org/our-network/>

List of WG:

Agriculture, Agri-Food & Rural

Culture & Creativity

Digital Urban Systems & Solutions for Transitions Urban Innovation

Education & Learning

Energy & Environment

Gender in Innovation

Harmonization

Health & Well Being

Mobility

Regenerative Tourism & Placemaking

Social Innovation & Digital Rights

Transition Super Living Labs

Water & Oceans

Agriculture, Agri-Food & Rural

Description: This WG fosters networking and knowledge exchange in agricultural Living Labs. It invites existing and aspiring labs to join the Network and collaborate within the ecosystem.

Culture & Co-creativity

Description: This WG aims to position Culture and Co-Creativity Living Labs as drivers for the co-creation of products and services with other sectors.

Digital Urban systems and Solutions for Transitions

Description: This WG aims to address the challenges faced by cities in establishing and maintaining effective, inclusive and dynamic urban ecosystems.

Education and Learning

Description: This WG aims to support the transformation of educational institutions and vocational training centers towards a more holistic, systemic and inclusive approach by using Living Labs as intermediaries for including all their relevant stakeholders in creating innovative education and learning environments, fostering knowledge generation and exchange.

Energy & Environment

Description: The aim of this WG is to generate a global movement toward a more sustainable society to solve complex challenges related to energy and environment.

Gender in Innovation

Description: The goal of this WG is to build a network of stakeholders that cooperates to increase gendered innovation, advancing on research and practice, capacity building, addressing its potential for opening new markets and for solving global challenges and European priorities.

Harmonization

Description: This WG has been established to define a Harmonization Framework with suggested processes, guidelines and recommendations on how Living Labs can perform their activities in a harmonized way that is widely accepted by the Living Lab community across the world.

Health & Well Being

Description: The mission of this WG is to activate and boost a collaborative ecosystem among Living Labs interested in the domains of Health and Well Being, giving visibility of their added value at the European and international level and attracting key actors within the public and private sector.

Mobility

Description: This WG supports knowledge sharing and collaboration among Mobility Living Labs. It fosters common understanding to address policy, scalability, sustainability, and joint EU-level positions.

Regenerative Tourism & Placemaking

Description: This WG reimagines the role of tourism and placemaking in cities, aiming for sustainability and active urban regeneration. Through Living Labs as spaces for testing and innovation, it develops new metropolitan practices that enhance quality of life, strengthen social cohesion, and enrich place identity.

Social Innovation & Digital Rights

Description: This WG is exploring how social innovation through Living Labs can help address societal challenges through concrete actions and by providing access for wider societies and communities to social innovation ecosystems.

Transition Super Living Labs

Description: This WG has been established to demonstrate the role of the Living Labs as transition accelerators that bridge bottom up and top-down policies and enable collaborative and cross sectorial innovation and synergies.

Water and Oceans

Description: This WG has been established to foster knowledge exchange between and to provide networking opportunities for all Living Labs and organisations involved in water and oceans.

Click [HERE](#) or scan the following QR code to sign up!

ENoLL Membership

How to become a member?

If you would like to become a member of ENoLL, the process starts by reaching out to the ENoLL Office at enollnetwork@enoll.org. From there, you can request all the details, clarifications, and application materials you will need.

The application is based on two main parts:

- A self-assessment tool (available online for free [here](#)), which gives a quantitative picture of your Living Lab's maturity, according to the ENoLL Harmonised Evaluation Framework and its criteria.
- A qualitative application form, where you can describe your Living Lab and its activities in more detail.

The application to become a member also foresees the payment of an evaluation fee of €600 (VAT excl.).

Once you receive the application package and all the relevant information, you will need to complete both the self-assessment and the qualitative form by one of the two yearly cut-off dates: 15 March or 15 October. The full application along with supporting materials and proof of payment of the evaluation fee, should be then sent to the ENoLL Office via email.

Every application is reviewed by three independent Living Lab experts in a peer-review process, and additional clarifications or details might be requested. Based on their consolidated feedback, the outcome can be: Rejected; Accepted as an Adherent Member; or Accepted as an Accepted to Grow Member.

Each applicant will then receive a full and customised evaluation report explaining the results. The final approval of new members is the given by the ENoLL General Assembly.

All details about becoming a member are available on ENoLL official website: <https://enoll.org/how-to-become-an-enoll-member-or-innovation-partner/>

Types of membership

ENoLL comprises four membership's categories: **Accepted to Grow Member, Adherent Member, Effective Member, and Innovation Partner.**

Applications for membership may be submitted **at any time but are only evaluated after the cut-off dates.** Since the establishment of ENoLL in 2006, this process has led to the recognition of more than 500 Living Labs worldwide.

Membership grants access to an international community of Living Labs engaged in collaborative research, projects development, networking, etc. It provides opportunities for exchange and cooperation with organisations across Europe and beyond, facilitated through ENoLL's communication channels, events, and Working Groups.

Membership applications can be submitted by any legal entity **from any country in the world** that operates or hosts (on behalf of a partnership) a Living Lab. Applicant organisation must demonstrate the capacity to operate as a Living Lab, to act as an innovation provider through the Living Lab methodology, and/or to develop their activities and operations towards Living Labs.

With reference to Innovation Partners, these are organizations or institutions that can provide significant added value to the network, demonstrate a genuine interest in participating in and developing network activities, and are not currently recognized or planning to be recognized as Living Labs. To become Innovation Partners, interested organisations can submit a formal request and expression of interest that will be **assessed by ENoLL Secretariat.**

Effective Members

The Effective members are Adherent Members that request, with a letter of intent, to upgrade their membership to Effective Membership. Each Effective Members enjoy a higher level of engagement within the Network; they can lead Working Groups, be elected as part of the ENoLL Council, represent ENoLL in high-level events organised at European and International level, join projects, etc. This status ensures a high degree of exposure, within the network and with

external stakeholders. Effective Member shall designate a representative to act on its behalf in the meetings of the General Assembly; furthermore, only Effective Members have rights to vote during general Assemblies.

Adherent Members

The Adherent members are Living Labs that have successfully obtained the ENoLL Certification. Adherent Members are entitled to join all the activities of the network, including peer-to-peer exchanges and collaborative initiatives, capacity building activities, projects, ENoLL Working Groups, join ENoLL events or in partnership with relevant other organisations, visibility on the website and on ENoLL social media. Adherent Members can join General Assembly and can speak, but they don't have any right to vote.

Accepted to Grow Members

Accepted to Grow Members are organizations that represent a Living Lab, which duly applied to the ENoLL certification process, but still not yet completely mature (according to the ENoLL Harmonised Evaluation Framework). This kind of certification only last one year, during which the organisation benefits from tailored guidance and access to ENoLL activities (research, projects, communication, capacity building, etc.) to further develop and refine their Living Lab operations. Participation in the Virtual Learning Lab (VLL) course is mandatory, ensuring that members acquire the necessary methodological knowledge and skills to align their practices. At the end of the one-year period, Accepted to Grow Members undergo a formal re-evaluation process to, hopefully, determine the transition to Adherent Membership.

Innovation Partners

Innovation partners are organisations that are not Living Labs themselves but embrace and share ENoLL's vision and actively contribute to the development, dissemination, and scaling up of Living Lab methodologies and activities. They do not undergo the ENoLL Labeling and certification process but are recognized as strategic allies of the network, reinforcing the exchange knowledge and fostering partnerships between Living Labs and relevant stakeholders and communities. Innovation partners can also join Working Groups, capacity building activities, projects, etc. Innovation Partners can join General Assembly and can speak, but they don't have any right to vote.

ENoLL Members map, numbers and countries

NEW NUMBERS 1 SEPT 2025:

ENoLL Members: 184	Effective Members: 27	Adherent Members: 142
Accepted to Grow: 11	Innovation Partner: 4	

Sectors

Living Labs can work in multiple sectors. Most of the ENoLL members have a transversal approach that allows them to focus on more than two sectors. This graph shows the different sectors in which ENoLL members work and offer their services.

Types of Living Labs

The mapping of the ENoLL members has shown a distribution of 5 main types of Living Labs.

The type of the Living Lab refers to the nature and service of each organization. Moreover, a Living Lab can belong to more than one type depending on their work. At ENoLL most of the Living Labs have pointed out their emphasis as Research Driven Living Lab and Living Lab as a service.

Fields of expertise

Living Labs in ANDORRA

Adherent Member

Andorra Living Lab

Andorra Recerca i
Innovació

Country: Andorra
andorralivinglab.com

Andorra Living Lab is the first living lab at country scale, a space for innovation projects coordination, research, design and validation that involves all actors in the same ecosystem, enabling for development of new products and services, as well as encouraging the adoption of new technologies and in-depth reflections on them.

The country provides the opportunity to create synergies among the entrepreneurial ecosystem, promoting talent and building networks that span both social and technological aspects.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Circular Economy
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Regulatory Learning
- SME & Start-ups
- Social innovation & inclusion
- Zero pollution & decarbonization

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Participatory Tools & Methods	Governance Modelling	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Scaling-up
Stakeholder Management	Living Lab Evaluation	Panel Management	Real-life Experimentation	User & Living Lab Research		

Living Labs in AUSTRALIA

Adherent Member

Central Coast Health & Wellbeing Living Lab

University of Newcastle and Central Coast Local Health District

Country: Australia
<https://www.ccll.com.au/>

The Central Coast Health & Wellbeing Living Lab (CCLL) supports innovation that helps people age well and strengthens community wellbeing. CCLL connects researchers, healthcare providers, older adults, carers, and local industry to develop solutions that address community and sector needs. It focus on community engagement and participatory methods, such as co-design, to help research and innovation projects access end-users, gather insights, and refine technologies and service models that reflect the priorities of older adults and those who support them.

CCLL ensures projects are grounded in lived experience, generate useful evidence, and deliver outcomes that make a measurable difference for individuals and communities, while strengthening the region's innovation ecosystem.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Health & Well Being
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

**Global Centre for
Modern Ageing**

Global Centre for
Modern Ageing

Country: Australia
www.gcma.net.au

The Global Centre for Modern Ageing (GCMA) is a not-for-profit organisation, and its purpose is to improve the lives of older people. Through advocacy, market development, partnerships, research, and learning, GCMA helps organisations and individuals to devise, build, and commercialise products and services that allow older people to live and age well. The Living Lab has deep expertise in end-user experience research, which brings fresh, evidence-based insights to the Ageing Well industry.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Health & Well Being
- Research
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Other areas of work

Main Expertise

 Scaling-up						
 User & Living Lab Research						

Adherent Member

Intergener8 Living Lab

Young and Resilient
Research Centre

Country: Australia
www.westernsydney.edu.au/young-and-resilient

The Intergener8 Living Lab is the engine room of the Young and Resilient Research Centre's co-research and design program and was co-created in 2017 with over 100 partners. Intergener8 provides research and co-design infrastructure to bring different generations, community, industry and government stakeholders together on a flexible and ongoing basis, supported by the Co-Research and Engagement Toolkit. Intergener8 Living Lab conducts research and design programs, services and policies. It also co-creates and trials new and potentially commercialisable products that significantly boost engagement, wellbeing, resilience and entrepreneurship by harnessing the potential of technology. The Intergener8 Living Lab is a founding member of the Australian Living Labs Innovation Network and was accredited in 2019 by ENoLL. Intergener8 has delivered ten Living Lab Projects between 2019-2021.

Areas of work

- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Media
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

 Stakeholder Management						
 User & Living Lab Research						

Adherent Member

Swinburne Living Lab

Swinburne University of Technology

Country: Australia

<https://www.swinburne.edu.au/research/centres-groups-clinics/centre-for-design-innovation/our-research/future-self-living-lab/>

Vision of the Living Lab is Wellbeing and Enjoyment for Whole of Life. Its mission is: “Enriching everyday living of older adults through co-design”. Its objectives are: i) to enhance wellbeing of older adults through development of products, services, and experiences; ii) to become national leaders in the co-design of products, services, and experiences for the wellbeing of older adults; iii) to conduct evidence-based research on the effectiveness of products, services, and experiences for older adults; iv) to advocate on policy and funding matters for the wellbeing of older adults with funders, regulators, and peak bodies; v) to increase the recognition of the potential and impact of the Living Lab concept and practice nationally and internationally; vi) to provide training in design through workshops and other activities.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Health & Well Being
- Mobility
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation

Participatory Tools & Methods

Impact Assessments

Implementation after Testing

Innovation Strategies

Policy Making

Scaling-up

Stakeholder Management

Living Lab Evaluation

Real-life Experimentation

Service Design

User & Living Lab Research

Living Labs in
AUSTRIA

Adherent Member

Prolida - Professional Living, Innovation and Development Lab for an Ageing Society

Carinthia University of Applied Sciences

Country: Austria
www.prolida.at

PROLIDA supports quadruple-helix stakeholders in the field of Health and Wellbeing (AAL/AHA) in the participative development, multi-perspective (real-life) evaluation, and long-term anchoring of innovations in the market. It focuses on technological innovations related to an active and healthy lifestyle, formal and informal care services and holistic health and wellbeing approaches.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Health & Well Being
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

StadtLABOR

StadtLABOR
Innovationen für urbane
Lebensqualität GmbH

Country: Austria
www.stadtlaborgraz.at

StadtLABOR (CityLAB) is a private innovation company working in the field of sustainable urban development. It is looking for ways in which climate protection, resource conservation and innovation can be given greater consideration in construction projects and in the development of locations, neighbourhoods, and urban districts. The vision of StadtLABOR is the liveable and sustainable city - that is resource-efficient, energy-efficient, compact, green, mixed, inclusive, and resilient. Urban quality of life requires a holistic view of the many facets of "city" - from buildings and (energy) technologies to public space, mobility and social issues. The Living Lab follows these principles: i) long-term partnerships: the transformation of a place takes time. It requires relationships that are supported by perseverance, a shared vision of the future and mutual trust; ii) out of the meeting room and into the place where the action is: this creates low-threshold accessible spaces for learning and working together, where people develop and implement solutions together; iii) rapid knowledge sharing, experimentation and prototyping: complex issues usually have more than one possible solution.

Areas of work

- Circular Economy
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Mobility
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

Agrotopia Living Lab

Inagro VZW

Country: Belgium

www.inagro.be

To stimulate sustainable urban and greenhouse horticulture, further developments are required in using residual streams (heat, water, and CO₂), recycling of resources, automatization, climatization and maximizing use of available space and energy efficiency. As the knowledge partner of agricultural and horticultural businesses in the areas of innovation and sustainability, Inagro tailors solutions to their needs. Inagro's new high tech research infrastructure to support the Living Lab is the 9000 sqm Agrotopia rooftop research greenhouse on top of the agricultural market in Roeselare. Six thousand sqm cultivation area, a compartment for multilayer indoor growing with artificial lighting and a 12 m high vertical compartment allow to co-create, develop, validate, and demonstrate innovative best practices for vegetable hydroponic systems. Agrotopia's location, at the agricultural auction market, where growers and buyers meet daily, offers a unique opportunity towards interactions. It allows researchers, growers, technology providers, knowledge institutions, educators, and society to meet, collaborate, and co-create. To further stimulate this multidisciplinary approach, Agrotopia provides a unique platform to the Ghent University Agrotopia endowed chair, and the greenhouse is open to the growers and the general public. The Agrotopia Living Lab delivers the services to realize co-creation in this unique setting.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food

Main Expertise

Participatory Tools & Methods	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Scaling-up	Stakeholder Management	Living Lab Evaluation
Panel Management	Real-life Experimentation	Service Design	User & Living Lab Research			

Living Labs in BELGIUM

Adherent Member

COMON – Living Lab Ghent

City of Ghent

Country: Belgium
www.stad.gent/en

COMON is an open Living Lab in Ghent, Belgium, where scientists, technologists, creatives, and citizens collaborate to co-create human-centered, technological solutions for complex urban challenges. Founded in 2020 by the City of Ghent, imec, Ghent University, and Library De Krook, COMON aligns with Ghent’s vision for inclusive and innovative urban development.

Based on state of the art methodologies COMON fosters a culture of experimentation, inclusivity, and continuous learning. It brings together citizens, researchers, policymakers, and entrepreneurs to tackle ‘wicked’ problems through tangible, real-world actions.

COMON’s initiatives include roundtables, rooftop events, co-creation workshops, and make-a-thons, resulting in impactful prototypes like Dolox (a wearable for pain patients), RingMe (a multilingual phone bot), ExplainMed (a medical document translator), and MIA (a mental health matchmaking platform).

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Health & Well Being
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social innovation & Inclusion
- Urban

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

Happy Aging

In4Care vzw

Country: Belgium
www.in4care.be

Happy Aging, the living lab of In4Care, is an inclusive ecosystem where companies, care organizations, knowledge institutions, and end users collaborate in a realistic and inspiring environment. Within this setting, innovative ideas are developed, tested, and refined to address both current and future challenges in healthcare. While Happy Aging has extensive expertise in elderly care and engaging active older adults, its focus extends to broader care innovation and prevention, recognizing that healthy aging begins well before old age. By placing end users firmly at the center, Happy Aging ensures that solutions are meaningful, practical, and ready for successful implementation.

Testing takes place in authentic contexts, such as lab and care facilities as well as people’s homes, providing a safe and relevant environment for co-creation, knowledge exchange, and the acceleration of adoption processes. Leveraging its strong expertise and close connections with a broad network of health care providers throughout Flanders, Happy Aging is uniquely positioned to bridge innovative concepts with daily practice.

Areas of work

- Health & Well Being

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

ILVO Marine Living Lab - The Covenant for sustainable sea fisheries in Belgium

ILVO - Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food
Country: Belgium
ilvo.vlaanderen.be

The ILVO Marine Living Lab is Flanders' open innovation hub for sustainable blue growth. Anchored in Ostend and backed by ILVO's 600-strong research institute, the lab links scientists, entrepreneurs, fishers, policy-makers and citizens in real-world co-creation trajectories. Stakeholders can tap into a mix of cutting-edge assets: state-of-the-art aquaculture halls, microbiology and chemistry suites, metocean sensor networks, land-sea robotics, and flexible access to research vessels for offshore trials. Within this sandbox new feeds, restorative coastal infrastructure, selective fishing gears and digital services are piloted from proof-of-concept to pre-market scale. Projects follow a living-lab methodology: beginning with a concrete industrial or societal question, multidisciplinary teams jointly design, prototype, validate and upscale solutions under authentic North Sea conditions while assessing ecological and socio-economic effects. The lab also acts as a neutral broker, steering partners through permits, funding calls and intellectual-property pathways. By accelerating innovation cycles and lowering entry barriers, the ILVO Marine Living Lab catalyses resilient seafood production, circular bio-resource use and climate-robust maritime value chains, delivering tangible impact across Europe's blue economy.

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation, Participatory Tools & Methods, Impact Assessments, Implementation after Testing, Innovation Strategies, Policy Making, Scaling-up, Stakeholder Management, Real-life Experimentation, Service Design

Effective Member

imec.livinglabs IMEC
Country: Belgium
www.imec-int.com

Imec offers researchers and entrepreneurs the chance to co-create and test their innovative solutions thoroughly with their target audience and stakeholders. The involvement of the end-users at an early stage of the development process makes it possible to tailor the innovation from the outset to real needs, habits, attitudes, and contextual factors. In that way products and services are better and have every chance of success on the market. The imec.livinglabs research includes users early on and all through the innovation process. This approach provides a solution to innovation thresholds and challenges such as: i) capturing, understanding, and validating users' interactions with products and services, at an early stage; ii) transforming ideas into prototypes users can interact within their daily context; iii) shaping '(minimum) viable products' through an iterative, agile process; iv) designing business models through stakeholder analysis and go-to-market definition.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Media
- Mobility
- Regulatory Learning
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban
- Water (Blue economy)
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation, Participatory Tools & Methods, Governance Modelling, Impact Assessments, Implementation after Testing, Innovation Strategies, Policy Making, Scaling-up, Stakeholder Management, Living Lab Evaluation, Panel Management, Real-life Experimentation, Service Design, User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

Agrotopia Living Lab

Inagro VZW

Country: Belgium
www.inagro.be

The Living Lab Circular of Inagro is aimed for optimising the role of agriculture in the circular economy through increased co-creation. This is not limited to circular solutions between farms but also between farms, industry, and society. Relevant themes within agriculture are water, nutrients, biomass, and energy. Examples of previous projects are converting the fibres from the stems of brussels sprouts into paper or testing cleaned wastewater from food industry as an irrigation source for vegetables. Also, anaerobic digestors can convert manure or food waste into heat, energy and upgraded fertilisers. The LLC exists of a network of 20 stakeholder organisations from each party within the quadruple helix (society, industry, research, government). Furthermore, all pilot installations available at Inagro could be used for research at a practical relevant scale. This includes, but is not limited to, insect halls, aquaculture, anaerobic digester, greenhouses, climate rooms, harvesters, fertilisers, etc.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Circular Economy
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Research
- Rural
- Soil
- Water (Blue Economy)

Main Expertise

Participatory Tools & Methods Policy Making Scaling-up Stakeholder Management Living Lab Evaluation Panel Management Service Design

User & Living Lab Research Real-life Experimentation

Adherent Member

JF OCEANS

SENSO2ME NV

Country: Belgium
senso2.me/en/

Senso2Me is a company based in Antwerp that produces technology and sells solutions to support the care of vulnerable persons in professional and residential environments. Senso2Me designs its own hardware, firmware, and cloud software to address market needs. Thanks to its innovative team, Senso2Me is able to follow and introduce novel technological and business opportunities to the market.

Areas of Work

- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation Participatory Tools & Methods Governance Modelling Impact Assessments Implementation after Testing Innovation Strategies Scaling-up

Stakeholder Management Service Design User & Living Lab Research

Effective Member

Licalab - Living and Care Lab	VZW Thomas More Kempen	Country: Belgium www.licalab.be
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LiCalab is a care living lab that supports businesses and organizations by including end users (citizens, patients, care professionals,...) from the very beginning of the development process until market introduction. LiCalab is a research group within Thomas More University of Applied Sciences. The Living Lab is strongly embedded in its region and has a large regional and international network on citizen, institutional, academic and policy level. The focus areas of LiCalab are medical care, (patient) rehabilitation, care technology, assisted living, active and healthy aging, and preventative healthcare. LiCalab gained extensive expertise in methodologies for co-creation, co-design, user experience, stakeholder engagement and participatory approaches and has experience in collaborating with Living Labs on an international scale.

Areas of Work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Health & Well Being
- Policies
- Regulatory Learning
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban

Main Expertise

 Stakeholder Management							
 User & Living Lab Research							

Adherent Member

Living Lab Animal Husbandry (LLAH)	ILVO - Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food	Country: Belgium ilvo.vlaanderen.be
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The Living Lab Animal Husbandry (LLAH) is hosted by Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (ILVO). Main goal of the LLLAH is promoting practice-oriented innovation in the pig, cattle and poultry industry by co-creation, knowledge exchange and controlled experiments in research facilities and on commercial farms. Unique characteristics of the LLAH arise from its combination of translating research towards practical implementation and innovation by the farmers and industry. Within the LLAH the Pig Information Center, Cattle Information Center and Poultry Information Center act as an easily accessible contact, meeting, and communication platform in Flanders, providing information for all stakeholders, and bringing together and integrating the needs of the stakeholders into future practice-based and demand-driven research and co-creation. Enhancing transfer of both scientific and tacit knowledge towards and between all stakeholders is essential for the competitiveness and sustainability of the Flemish livestock sector.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Circular Economy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Rural
- Water (Blue economy)
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

 Stakeholder Management							
 User & Living Lab Research							

Adherent Member

Smart Retail City Lab

SA FS Brussels
Agentschap voor de
Ondersteuning van het
Bedrijfsleven

Country: Belgium

www.smart-retail-city-lab.com

A Smart Retail City is a city with a detailed knowledge of urban commerce, the customer, and trends. Initiated by Hub.brussels, the Smart Retail City Lab is a user-centred research and innovation project. Its objective is to lead the Brussels-Capital Region along the path of the Smart Retail City.

Areas of work

- Smart Cities & Regions

Main Expertise

Business
Model
Innovation

Participatory
Tools &
Methods

Impact
Assessments

Implementation
after Testing

Innovation
Strategies

Stakeholder
Management

Panel
Management

Service
Design

User & Living
Lab Research

Adherent Member

ZorgLab Aalst

GEMEENTE Stad Aalst

Country: Belgium

aalst.be/zorglab-aalst

Zorglab Aalst is a living lab in health and care. It is an environment to test and experiment with innovative solutions in health and care. Zorglab Aalst supports and collaborates with entrepreneurs, researchers, policymakers and health care organizations in citizen-centered and/or patient-centred solutions. It provides advice, matchmaking of partners, co-creation and testing in real life. Zorglab Aalst makes a demonstration residence available in which the latest new applications, infrastructure and services can be demonstrated to the citizens/elderly/patients and care professionals themselves. The living lab is focusing on: Ageing in place, accessibility and adjusted housing; Age-friendly environments; Health & Care Tech; Prevention in health care; Collaboration in care and primary care.

Areas of work

- Health & Well Being

Main Expertise

Participatory
Tools &
Methods

Governance
Modelling

Impact
Assessments

Implementation
after Testing

Innovation
Strategies

Policy
Making

Scaling-up

Stakeholder
Management

Living Lab
Evaluation

Panel
Management

Real-life
Experimentation

Service
Design

User & Living
Lab Research

Adherent Member

Prijedor Circle HubPREDA (Development
agency of the city of
Prijedor)**Country: Bosnia &
Herzegovina**www.prijedorhub.com

Prijedor Circle Hub is the first Living Lab operating in Bosnia and Herzegovina created and managed by PREDA, the Development Agency of the City of Prijedor in the Republika Srpska. PREDA has been the Lead partner in the Interreg Cross-border Cooperation 2014-2020 project entitled Creative@CBC, which has involved similar pathways leading to an application to the ENoLL three organizations from Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia and Montenegro. Within the process of preparation of the project proposal, as well as during its implementation, PREDA recognized that a number of previous projects managed throughout the past 5 years, which are reported herein, were clearly inspired by the Living Lab approach. The Prijedor Circle Hub belongs to PREDA and is supported by 16 institutions and organizations originating from the 4 communities of the quadruple-helix. Its functioning is mainly project-based, though this does not necessarily mean that all activities are financially covered by specific funding sources. In fact, the decision to create a Living Lab and apply to become an ENoLL member is part of a strategic decision and a long-term commitment to user-driven, open innovation as an instrument to create a fertile environment for business investments and the creation of new entrepreneurship in the area, which are the two main missions of PREDA as Development agency of the city of Prijedor.

Living Labs in **BOSNIA & HERZEGOVINA**

Adherent Member

GATE City Living Lab

GATE Institute, Sofia
University "St. Kliment
Ohridski"

Country: Bulgaria

<https://gate-ai.eu/en/home/>

The City Living Lab is a research unit driven by the aspiration to solve contemporary urban challenges by engaging communities and utilizing spatial data, algorithms and interdisciplinary expertise. It provides a space where innovative technologies and participatory approaches come together to create more sustainable, efficient, and livable urban environments. With a strong focus on advancing urban innovation through technology, the lab develops and implements tools such as spatial data analytics and AI-driven models to improve urban planning, environment monitoring, and sustainable mobility. The City Living Lab serves as a bridge between research and real-world applications, providing municipalities, planners, and businesses with the necessary data, tools, and expertise to drive urban transformation.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Mobility
- Research
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Urban
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

Participatory
Tools &
Methods

Stakeholder
Management

User & Living
Lab Research

Living Labs in BULGARIA

Adherent Member

SofiaLab Sofia Development Association **Country: Bulgaria**
www.sofia-da.eu

SofiaLab is an Urban Living Lab – a Smart City community infrastructure and ecosystem, promoting urban innovations and local development by bringing together leading actors from public administration, academia, industry, and social organisations. The unique feature of SofiaLab is that it is a means for the development and implementation of Sofia Smart Specialisation Strategy which has the concept of Smart City in the core. SofiaLab is the hub of many Living Lab nodes in the city. It aims to establish an experimentation and makerspace to motivate further piloting of digital innovations within the smart city context. SofiaLab aims to encourage bottom-up idea generation, open innovation, and value co-creation at the centre of its maker space for active experimentation and pilot testing. SofiaLab hosts countless events and social activities such as awareness campaigns, community workshops and trainings, hackathons, research and innovation, start-up acceleration, social events, digital technologies camps, venture capital related events, technology transfer and company matchmaking and others.

Areas of work

- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Gender
- Health & Well Being
- Mobility
- Regulatory Learning
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

 Scaling-up						
 User & Living Lab Research						

Living Labs in CANADA

Adherent Member

Llio - Living lab en innovation ouverte

Cegep de Rivière-du-Loup

Country: Canada
www.llio.quebec

The Open Innovation Living Lab (LLio) is a centre for research and transfer of open innovative practices. Its mission is to facilitate the adoption of open innovation practices, in particular those involving users. The LLio's field is a research centre that intervenes in innovative social practices, both in the context of social and technological innovation. As its specialty concerns the adoption of open innovation practices, it explores, experiments, adapts, develops, and applies methods, devices, and tools such as Fab Lab, Design Thinking/Service Design, co-creation, empathy, serious games, and prototyping. LLio mainly uses the Living Lab approach to oversee the deployment of these tools and principles. The Centre does research and intervention in open innovation. To succeed in this transfer role, the LLio is interested in: i) OI practices, actors, spaces, and scales; ii) the capacity to innovate of people, organizations, and territories; iii) the evaluation of this capacity and its impact.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Regulatory Learning
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation

Participatory Tools & Methods

Governance Modelling

Impact Assessments

Innovation Strategies

Scaling-up

Stakeholder Management

Living Lab Evaluation

Real-life Experimentation

Service Design

User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

Mandalab

Communautique

Country: Canada
www.communautique.quebec

The Mandalab is a Living Lab network, hosted by Communautique. Communautique is a Montreal-based non-profit urban community network founded in 1995 to assist low-income individuals and families and other groups potentially excluded from participating in the information society. It provides Internet access and other ICT services and training throughout the province of Québec. In addition, Communautique has raised public awareness of the potential impact of provincial government online initiatives on the voluntary sector and the populations its serves. Communautique was invited to present its actions as part of the Quebec delegation to the World Summit on Information Society in Tunis. Communautique is also active in building ICT capacity within the voluntary sector itself to enable community groups to work more effectively to accomplish their goals. Communautique is actively involved in Industry Canada's Information Management/Information Technology (IM/IT) program, which aims to increase the technological capacity of the voluntary sector in Canada.

Areas of work

- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Social Innovation

Adherent Member

Rehabilitation Living Lab in the mall

Centre for Interdisciplinary Research in Rehabilitation of greater Montreal (CRIR)

Country: Canada
www.facebook.com/LaboratoireVivant

The Rehabilitation Living Lab in the mall (RehabMaLL) project is the first interdisciplinary and multi-sectorial research study aiming to explore the principal obstacles and facilitators, whether physical or psychosocial, to social participation and inclusion for persons with disabilities in a commercial mall environment. The project is conducted by the Centre for Interdisciplinary Research in Rehabilitation of Greater Montreal (CRIR). It is in the process of transforming an urban shopping mall, Alexis Nihon, in downtown Montreal, into an inclusive environment for individuals of all ages, particularly for those with disabilities, to create an ecologically valid example of a societal microcosm where complex transactions and activities involving persons with and without disabilities take place year-round.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Health & Well Being
- Mobility
- Rural
- Social Innovation

Living Labs in **CHINA**

Adherent Member

Living Lab SHANGHAI

Tongji University

Country: China

LivingLab SHANGHAI is an educational platform based on the open approach and environment of the Sino-Finnish Centre, located at Tongji University. It promotes open innovation for generating social construction of knowledge, bridging top-down and bottom-up social innovation processes in real-world contexts by involving relevant stakeholders. Its main characteristics are: i) education-based research and practice: bridging the gaps between education, research and practice in the real world context; ii) design-driven application of new technology: a design-driven approach for complex social problems, involving a mix of human and societal needs where solutions employ new technology; iii) multi-stakeholder ecosystem: the ongoing development of eco-system consisting of enterprises, entrepreneurs, universities, research institutes, associations and other NGOs.

Living Labs in **COLOMBIA**

Adherent Member

Living Lab Sabana

Universidad de La Sabana

Country: Colombia
livinglabsabana.com

The Living Lab of Universidad de la Sabana is a concept of collective intelligence materialized in scenarios that integrate the academic, research, and social projection ecosystem centred on the territory and the people that are part of the region, acting as an organic co-creation platform and promoting applied knowledge through the generation of capacities in innovation and startups; the LL is a pioneer in the region and in Colombia, exploring new technologies to foster creation and creativity, seeking solutions to various challenges, promoting open innovation and developing prototypes to foster experiential learning. The management model of the LL is responsible for co-creation, prototyping, evaluation, and gamification processes, promoting active participation in specialized practical learning to develop new solutions, with a positive impact on the quadruple helix. Through new methodologies, tools, and technologies it contributes to the generation of new ecosystems of innovation.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation

Participatory Tools & Methods

Impact Assessments

Implementation after Testing

Innovation Strategies

Stakeholder Management

Living Lab Evaluation

User & Living Lab Research

Real-life Experimentation

Living Labs in CROATIA

Adherent Member

Pismo Hub

Sisak Moslavina County Development Agency for encouraging economic development, consulting and representation (SI-MO-RAItd)

Country: Croatia

www.inkubator-pismo.eu

The initiative started as the Business Incubator Pismo Novska (focused on game development, AI, and blockchain technology) and later evolved into the first Living Lab in the Sisak-Moslavina County, and first to have the aim of using AI, gaming and blockchain technology solutions in digital transition and debureaucratization of public administration, which has been recognized as the County's major problem for years. Pismo Hub has established quality long-term relations with different groups of stakeholders (NGOs, government, academia, and private sector), given the type of business its host organization does as a regional development agency and due to its extensive network of business partners. The host organization is also a part of a number of renowned consortiums – Digital Innovation Hub DIGI SI DIH, Digital Innovation Hub Blockchain for Trusted Data Ecosystems, European Digital Innovation Hub for Smart Health, ARAGÓN DIH and other partnerships in this particular field. After the end of a pilot project in one local public administration unit, it is expected that other cities and municipalities will adopt the serious game and blockchain-based CRM program solutions in their own administration and city finances.

Adherent Member

Rijeka iLivingLab

Faculty of Economics and Mangement, University of Rijeka

Country: Croatia

riill.efri.uniri.hr

Rijeka Innovation Living Lab (RiILL), hosted by the Faculty of Economics and Business at the University of Rijeka, is a user-centered, open-innovation ecosystem designed to support sustainable urban and economic transformation. Grounded in the quadruple-helix model, RiILL brings together academia, government, businesses, and citizens to co-create, test, and scale solutions in real-life settings. It serves as a dynamic platform for applied research, digital innovation, and community-driven experimentation.

Structured around seven thematic labs, RiILL addresses twelve interconnected research areas, including smart cities, regenerative economy, smart governance, digital transformation, AI and data engineering, and the EU Green Deal. Its mission is to foster participatory innovation through living pilots, co-creation workshops, and knowledge transfer activities that directly support public and private sector transformation.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Circular Economy
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation

Participatory Tools & Methods

Governance Modelling

Impact Assessments

Implementation after Testing

Innovation Strategies

Policy Making

Scaling-up

Stakeholder Management

Living Lab Evaluation

Panel Management

Real-life Experimentation

Service Design

User & Living Lab Research

Living Labs in CZECH REPUBLIC

Accepted to Grow

PROBIO Living Lab

Czech Organics

Country: Czech Republic

<https://www.eco-ready.eu/living-labs/probio/>

The PROBIO Living Lab is an organic, on-farm Living Lab that demonstrates how organic farming can offer real, practical solutions to climate and environmental challenges. Located in South Moravia, Czech Republic – one of the most fertile but also most drought-prone regions in the country – the lab provides a real-world testing ground for innovative and resilient approaches rooted in organic principles. CZPROLL focuses on three main areas: improving climate resilience and soil fertility in organic systems; adapting crop and livestock production to drought and erosion-prone conditions; enhancing knowledge sharing and implementation into practice among organic farmers.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Circular Economy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Rural
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Soil
- Water (Blue Economy)
- Other areas of work: Food

Main Expertise

 Stakeholder Management						
 Real-life Experimentation						

Adherent Member

Danish organic on-farm living lab	Innovation Center for Organic Farming	Country: Denmark icoel.dk/
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The Danish Organic on-farm Living Lab (DKOFLL) is a national holistic network where there is the opportunity to experiment and bring into practice innovative solutions for organic farming. The DKOFLL works within three key areas: (1) building up and maintaining soil fertility; (2) develop efficient and resilient cropping systems; and (3) improve animal welfare. Each area covers a diverse portfolio of projects, stakeholders and farms, driving the development through specific measures and expertise.

As the manager organisation, the Innovation Centre for Organic Farming, has long experience in co-creation, setting up, running and funding activities within living labs located in organic farms, involving farmers, advisory services, universities, research institutes and local government as well as producers and retailers.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Environment/Climate Change

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Participatory Tools & Methods	Governance Modelling	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Scaling-up
Stakeholder Management	Living Lab Evaluation	Panel Management	Real-life Experimentation	Service Design	User & Living Lab Research	

Living Labs in DENMARK

Adherent Member

**ENERGY & WATER -
Greater Copenhagen
Living Lab**

City of Copenhagen

Country: Denmark
www.energiogvand.dk

ENERGY & WATER – Greater Copenhagen Living Lab co-creates and tests tools for education, showcasing and citizen involvement that underpin the creation of sustainable city solutions. ENERGY & WATER is a collaboration between HOFOR (the largest utility company in Denmark) and the City of Copenhagen (the capital of Denmark).

Areas of work

- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Urban
- Water (Blue Economy)
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

Governance Modelling	Participatory Tools & Methods	Implementation after Testing	Stakeholder Management	Living Lab Evaluation	Real-life Experimentation	Service Design

Living Labs in FINLAND

Adherent Member

CODER Living Lab LUT University **Country: Finland**
<https://www.lut.fi/en>

CODER is an ICT-enabled Living Lab entirely dedicated to the innovation, development and validation of software systems, products and services with a human mind-set. It combines a physical smart environment that motivates open innovation, a cloud-based toolbox and equipment to develop and validate a wide range of user experience-centric software products, systems and services, as well as the large network of stakeholders and technology partners that provide the best business and technical competence and mentoring to the drivers of software technology innovation. The Lab aims to be a place for effective and efficient engagement of a large pool of user communities and all stakeholders in all the stages of the software development and innovation lifecycle. CODER is the place for changing the human mind-set using software products, systems and services. The Lab is currently supporting research in the following areas: i) human-data interaction for data literacy; ii) participatory sensing and civic tech; iii) data and technology for ‘More-than-human’ and sustainable urban design; iv) smart cities; v) energy citizenship.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Mobility
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

Participatory Tools & Methods Governance Modelling Implementation after Testing Innovation Strategies Policy Making Scaling-up Stakeholder Management

Service Design Real-life Experimentation User & Living Lab Research

Innovation Partner

Finnish Network of Living Labs South-Eastern Finland University of Applied Sciences XAMK **Country: Finland**

Finnish Network of Living Labs is a co-orchestrated platform of six Finnish universities of applied sciences. The platform originated at the time of the founding of ENoLL. The innovation partnership includes: Xamk South-Eastern Finland University of Applied Sciences, Haaga-Helia University of Applied Sciences, Savonia University of Applied Sciences, Centria University of Applied Sciences, Arcada University of Applied Sciences, and Häme University of Applied Sciences. The partnership embeds and develops Living Lab praxis with corporate and NGO partners in southern, eastern, and western Finland with the help of over 30 000 students and 3000 staff. The partnership is committed to: i) cooperation in national and international project planning and execution; ii) enhancing the international visibility of Finnish Living Labs; and iii) making an impact in the worldwide ENoLL community. Finnish Network of Living Labs is coordinated by Xamk. The network represents different types of Living Labs and is thus well-suited to explore best practices and exchange ideas, especially, about how to embed Living Lab methodology into local and regional development. The network operates through regular live co-learning forums which are open to international ENoLL partners in addition to online working groups.

Areas of work

- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Health & Well Being
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation Participatory Tools & Methods Governance Modelling Impact Assessments Implementation after Testing Innovation Strategies Policy Making

Scaling-up Stakeholder Management Living Lab Evaluation Panel Management Real-life Experimentation Service Design User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

Forum Virium Helsinki Forum Virium Helsinki **Country: Finland**
www.forumvirium.fi

Forum Virium Helsinki is the city of Helsinki's innovation company, it co-creates urban futures with companies, universities, public sector, and residents. FVH has a portfolio of 30+ innovation projects with international and national funding and employs 50+ experts. The innovation projects are planned and run in tight collaboration with the city of Helsinki's divisions. The topics range from data and novel technologies, mobility, adaptation to climate change and biodiversity, wellbeing and urban development. FVH's work is based on real-life experimentation with agile piloting programmes, using data and novel technologies for co-creation of smart and green solutions in collaboration with SME's and innovation ecosystems, and active engagement of the residents. In the Helsinki Innovation Districts, the best practices are taken from the novel development areas to the districts under regeneration.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Mobility
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban
- Water (Blue Economy)
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation, Participatory Tools & Methods, Governance Modelling, Impact Assessments, Implementation after Testing, Innovation Strategies, Policy Making, Scaling-up, Stakeholder Management, Living Lab Evaluation, Panel Management, Real-life Experimentation, Service Design, User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

Lahti Living Lab LUT University **Country: Finland**
www.lut.fi

The special focus of the Lahti Living Lab is to integrate the users into the innovation processes of public and private sector innovation and development focusing on all dimensions of sustainability and digitalization. For this purpose, methods and tools are developed and studied to fully enable knowledge creation and exploitation between users and professional developers. The methods of involving and activating the users vary, the encounters take place online but also face-to-face. Lahti Living Lab is implemented through research and development projects, which all have a common nominator, e.g. the users as active co-creators.

Areas of work

- Circular Economy
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Mobility
- Policies
- Research
- Rural
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation, Participatory Tools & Methods, Innovation Strategies, Policy Making, Stakeholder Management, Living Lab Evaluation, Service Design, User & Living Lab Research, Real-life Experimentation

Effective Member

Laurea Living Labs Network

Laurea University of Applied Sciences

Country: Finland
www.laurea.fi/en/research

LAUREA helps companies, public sector, academia, and citizens to co-create and pilot better innovations in various industrial domains. Living Lab provides professional know-how and education in Health and Wellbeing, Social Services, Correctional Services, Safety, Security and Risk Management, Business Management and Service Innovation, Circular Economy, Hospitality Management and Service Design, as well as Beauty and Cosmetics. LAUREA aims to make innovation more open, inclusive, and collaborative. Co-creation and experimentation do not happen without mediation. At LAUREA it is called 'orchestration'. LAUREA motivates businesses, researchers, public sector players and citizens to come together and innovate. Product development at the customer interface drastically reduces costs and time for launching. Collaboration with academia and businesses turns state-of-art research effectively into products and services. For citizens and public sector players, co-creation and innovation bring about better and more suitable services at reduced costs. Openness and free flow of information and ideas make processes more efficient and benefit all stakeholders. Adherence to open science, open innovation and open learning is LAUREA's competitive advantage. LAUREA's fields of expertise in RDI activities are holistic health and well-being, coherent security, service innovations and business models, entrepreneurship, and pedagogy.

Effective Member

TAMK Living Lab

Tampere University of Applied Sciences

Country: Finland
www.tuni.fi

TAMK Living Lab focuses on promoting co-creative solutions for green, digital and just transitions. Our transdisciplinary Living Lab projects and initiatives promote data-driven experimentation and demonstration in real-life settings. They combine themes such as climate neutrality, smart cities energy, circular economy, health and wellbeing, culture, and security and safety in an environmentally, economically and socially sustainable way. Our projects and initiatives dedicated to knowledge valorisation are always conducted with our committed network of partnerships representing all quadruple helix stakeholder groups. Specific focus is set on collaboration with SMEs and smaller business entities. TAMK Living Lab as an effective member of ENoLL since 2009 is strongly committed to the Living Lab approach, embedding it holistically to all its activities in R&I, education, and capacity building.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Mobility
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Participatory Tools & Methods	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Policy Making	Scaling-up
Stakeholder Management	Living Lab Evaluation	Panel Management	Real-life Experimentation	Service Design	User & Living Lab Research	

Living Labs in FRANCE

Adherent Member

Brie'Nov	Brie'Nov	Country: France www.brienov.fr
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Brie'Nov is an ecosystem of territorial and social innovation, both civic and digital. It is a melting pot that brings together various stakeholders (central place of the user). The Living Lab label encourages research, development, and collaboration. B'N promotes the challenge of digital as an opportunity for opening up and re-socializing. Brie'Nov is made up of entrepreneurs, local politicians, non-profit organizations, researchers, teachers and local residents. Main axes of work are based on a tripartite "bet" underpinning several projects: i) high-speed digital networks as a vector for overall development; ii) high-speed digital networks as a vector for opening up backwaters; iii) high-speed digital networks as a vector for social reintegration. Brie'Nov has also been labelled a Territory Factory (www.fabrique77.fr) and Territorial Pole of Economic Cooperation. These two national systems enable the Living Lab to accelerate various projects.

Areas of work

- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Mobility
- Rural
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

 Stakeholder Management						
 User & Living Lab Research						

Adherent Member

E2L Earth observation Living Labs

E2L Earth observation Living Labs

Country: France
www.e2l-coop.eu

The aim of the cooperative society Earth observation Living Labs (E2L) is to develop the use of space technologies based on the tools of geospatial information, to serve rural territories, by co-designing innovative solutions to create value and to improve existing practices. The central idea of the Living Lab focuses on the concept of regional Living Labs: E2L proposes a set of contexts (ways of expressing requirements for users, testing and demonstrations), to prove the usefulness of the applications of research and development activities in space technologies. The aim of E2L is to support the creation of new services by placing the end user in the position of being a co-developer on the scale of publicly managed territories. E2L continues to develop the method initiated in the area of Pays Portes de Gascogne which has been the creation of a Pôle d'Expérimentation et d'Application des technologies spatiales – PATS (an experimentation cluster on the use of space technologies). This cluster functions as an instrument enabling the adaptation of structural changes of the local economy to help emerging a new dynamic and competitive knowledge economy, based on the ability to experiment, on the local/regional scale.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Water (Blue Economy)

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

Gérontopôle Nouvelle-Aquitaine

Gérontopôle Nouvelle-Aquitaine

Country: France
www.gerontopole-na.fr

Gérontopôle Nouvelle-Aquitaine is a centre of expertise, support and action for active and healthy ageing well in the Nouvelle-Aquitaine region. It is a public organisation founded by the Regional Health Agency of Nouvelle-Aquitaine and the Nouvelle-Aquitaine Region, that brings together stakeholders for the active and healthy ageing: institutions; local authorities; research, training and innovation organisations; sanitary and social structures; user associations; businesses. It also works at EU level to exchange and develop responses to the demographic challenges. Thanks to its user-centred and cross-sectoral approach, it supports the development of services and devices with users and professionals. It aims at encouraging multidisciplinary research to improve the quality of life of older people, promoting local initiatives, innovating and supporting organisational, educational, professional and technological experiments and the development of local economy focused on ageing well.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Health & Well Being
- Mobility
- Policies
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

HA&WB LL Healthy Aging & Well Being Gerontopole Auvergne

Gérontopôle Auvergne Rhône-Alpes (Gérontopôle AURA)

Country: France

The Healthy Ageing and Well-Being Living Lab (HA&WB LL) is supported by a non-profit organization the Gérontopôle Auvergne Rhône-Alpes (Gérontopôle AURA). The objective of the Healthy Ageing and Well-Being Living Lab is to explore and achieve, policies and business goals related to health, well-being and active ageing, as well as social inclusion of seniors. HA&WB Living Lab is established as a nucleus for open innovation activities and as a repository of relevant knowledge and expertise. It sets up, coordinates, facilitates and manages research using various settings.

Adherent Member

ICT Usage Lab

Centre Inria d'Université Côte d'Azur

Country: France
www.ictusagelab.fr

ICT Usage Lab promotes multidisciplinary studies on usage-based innovation and coordinates researchers from different fields: artificial intelligence, computer science, data science, educational science, cognitive psychology and ergonomics, sociology, economics, etc. ICT Usage Lab aims at sharing its infrastructure (hardware, software, tools, etc.), as well as experiences and know-how. ICT Usage Lab is tackling challenges mainly in the field of digital science education: it aims at co-creating new educational materials in digital science with many involved actors (e.g. teachers, researchers, associations, entrepreneurs) to make people (children, pupils, students, citizens) understand the basics of computer science and to facilitate the dissemination of the digital science culture. The approach remains multidisciplinary and considers the latest research in innovative training, pedagogy and education. In parallel, the ICT Usage Lab also trains teachers in these new innovative teaching methods.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

La Fabrique du Futur La Fabrique du Futur **Country: France**
www.lafabriquedufutur.global

The mission of La Fabrique du Futur is to help organisations (local authorities, companies, NGOs) to imagine and build desirable futures. The Living Lab promotes co-creation and collective intelligence. It is committed to “Techs for Good” approaches such as the use of 3D, virtual reality and metaverses. La Fabrique du Futur is promoting the concept of distributed Living Lab to accompany better the ongoing transitions needed by our planet.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

 Policy Making						
 User & Living Lab Research						

Adherent Member

Living Lab Saint Victor Housing Society Elderly Resources Centre **Country: France**

Living Lab Saint Victor is situated In Amiens, France. Its easily accessible facilities and infrastructures are included in the University Hospital of Amiens and are adapted to conduct ecological studies in various living places, inpatients and outpatients wards. Living Lab Saint Victor objective is to be an efficient structure to test collaboratively from experimentation to use value, an idea, a technology or a solution and researches focused on technology for older adults and their caregivers. Living Lab Saint Victor provide expertise at different stages of the process. Living Lab aims to become a meeting place where actors from different disciplines, expertise and perspectives, will mutually enrich each other while collaborating together, and finally to attract investors and partners.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Health & Well Being
- Media
- Mobility
- Regulatory Learning
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

 Living Lab Evaluation					
 Real-life Experimentation					

Adherent Member

Lorraine Smart Cities Living Lab

Université de Lorraine -
Laboratoire ERPI

Country: France
www.lf2l.fr

Based on the universality of the university and its multidisciplinary, the Lorraine Smart Cities Living Lab (LSCLL) experiments in terms of projects, governance, and support platform since 2008. The LSCLL is a collaborative resource centre of the Université de Lorraine, to support and link the various thematic and territorial labs integrating users and implementing collaborative approaches in the service of research, development of innovations, training, and a citizen culture. ENOLL member since 2010 (4th wave), the LSCLL seeks to develop Public Private Population Partnerships (PPPPs) to disseminate innovation and related practices. Since 2014, the Lorraine Fab Living Lab® (LF2L) platform strengthens the Living Lab approach. This “innovation space” provides resources and 2D/3D/4D technologies allowing prospective assessment of innovative usages. The LSCLL brings together several teams from the University of Lorraine.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Circular Economy
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Policies
- Research
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Soil
- Urban
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization
- Other areas of work

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

MedTechLab®

Ecole Nationale Supérieure des Mines de Saint Etienne (Ecole de l'Institut Mines-Télécom) & AESIO Santé

Country: France
www.aesio-sante.fr

MedTechLab® is an interdisciplinary meeting space to think, to co-create, to model, to test, to experiment, and to assess the use of products and/or services incorporating new technologies in the fields of Health and Autonomy in a controlled environment and in a real-life environment. Human resources, areas and equipment are dedicated to MedTechLab®. MedTechLab® provides collective intelligent workshops based on Design Thinking methodology. In addition, MedTechLab® has a testbed consisting in a “smart apartment” equipped with different sensors (presence sensor/motion sensor) and cameras/analysers. The partnership between AESIO Santé and Mines - Saint Etienne is a major advantage. Engineers, scientists, students, and pedagogical engineers are available through the partnership with Ecole Nationale Supérieure des Mines de Saint-Etienne (Mines Saint-Etienne). Users and Health Professionals (general practitioners, medical specialists, healthcare assistants...) are available through the partnership with AESIO Santé. The test-bed available in the Living Lab, MedTechLab®, is the opportunity to test products and/or services in a controlled environment. Experiments, in a real-life environment, are conducted in medico-social and health-care establishments.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Health & Well Being
- SME & Start-ups

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

Nantes City Lab

Nantes Metropole

Country: France

www.metropole.nantes.fr/nantes-city-lab

Through the Nantes City Lab, Nantes Métropole provides a range of experimental sites, equipment, data, and engineering services to test innovative solutions in situ, in vivo, at scale 1. Nantes City Lab is a system dedicated to full-scale experimentation of innovative solutions by start-ups, SMEs, large groups, researchers, universities, and associations. It brings together concrete means to innovate in the Nantes metropolitan area, including:

- An urban laboratory: places and equipment to test innovative solutions related to social, ecological, and economic transitions.
- A service to facilitate innovation through experimentation: a single point of contact, labelling, research for places to experiment, links with Nantes Métropole technical departments, search for partnerships, definition of citizen interactions adapted to the projects, monitoring of experimentation, evaluation, and promotion.

Areas of work

- Circular Economy
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Mobility
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

Policy Making	Participatory Tools & Methods	Implementation after Testing	Scaling-up	Stakeholder Management	Living Lab Evaluation	Real-life Experimentation

Adherent Member

Normandy Living Lab

Pôle TES

Country: France

www.pole-tes.com

Normandy Living Lab's focus is on the efficient development of innovative products and services in the fields of digital agriculture, industry, health, smart territories, and creative digital content, by systematically placing the product or service user at the heart of the innovation process. Thanks to its wide variety of members and its continuous work with local authorities and communities, NLL is building a life-size testing environment covering all of Normandy. That way, it aims at being a vector for the co-creation of digital innovations, between designers and end-users, for a wide number of economic sectors.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Media
- Mobility
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Urban

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Participatory Tools & Methods	Governance Modelling	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Stakeholder Management
Living Lab Evaluation	Real-life Experimentation	Service Design	User & Living Lab Research			

Adherent Member

**Pasteur Innovative
Living Lab of Nice**

PAILLON 2020

Country: France

Created in 2009 by the French Ministry of the Economy, Industry and Employment, the CNR Santé (National Reference Centre for Homecare and Independent Living) is an association that brings together a large number of stakeholders focused on healthcare innovation. As part of the portfolio of CNR offerings, “PAILLON 2020” Living Lab fosters the emergence and growth of digital technologies in the domain of Homecare and Independent Living. The Healthcare Innovation Center that hosts the Living Lab was launched in 2015 and is co-run by the Healthcare Directorate and the Nice Metropolis. The aim of the Healthcare Innovation Center is to establish an ecosystem of innovative companies, researchers and institutions focused on the field of ageing, autonomy, digital healthcare, as well as social innovations in health. Living Lab PAILLON 2020 located in close proximity to the newest hospital in Nice (Hôpital Pasteur 2) and is geared for evaluation, discovery and uptake of innovative healthcare technologies, in particular, devices used by patients in their homes. The Living Lab is equipped with a model apartment that is designed as a showcase and a testing platform for technologies supporting independent living and autonomy.

Adherent Member

Réunion Living Lab

Technopole de La
Réunion

Country: France

<https://www.technopole-reunion.com/>

Reunion Living Lab is led by Technopole de La Réunion, a key innovation hub located in the French overseas region of La Réunion, in the Indian Ocean. Anchored in a multicultural and biodiversity-rich territory, the Lab promotes user-centred, collaborative innovation addressing social and environmental challenges.

As part of the regional University Innovation Hub (PUI Valiotech), Reunion Living Lab develops and supports real-life experimentation processes involving researchers, public institutions, grassroots organisations, businesses, and citizens.

Its focus is on inclusive and sustainable innovation in various fields such as digital technology and biodiversity, social innovation, climate risks, agri-food, economic activities, and tropical construction.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Circular Economy
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban
- Other areas of work

Adherent Member

Smart City Living Lab Dédale **Country: France**
www.dedale.info

The SmartCity Living Lab invites creative people, companies, researchers, and urban planners to come and test in situ and in vivo innovative solutions and services. The main themes of the SmartCity Living Lab are public space, circular economy, sustainable city, zero carbon, mobility, urban agriculture, citizen participation, smart city, sport and culture. The SmartCity Living Lab is financed by the Region (PICRI), the Ministry of Culture, and Europe (eContent+). It has enabled the implementation of experiments in the heart of the campus of the Cité Internationale Universitaire and has laid the foundations of the first urban Living Lab in Paris: i) these experiments accompany the territorial development and urban projects of the Greater Paris region and take the form of pilots and prototypes involving local actors, users, and inhabitants of the concerned territories; ii) these experiments have led to the development of digital tools in the context of participatory approaches involving the inhabitants and users of Paris and the southern suburbs and allowed Dedale to initiate Domaine Public, a research and experimentation programme on public space.

Areas of work

- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Mobility
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban

Main Expertise

 Scaling-up						
 User & Living Lab Research						

Adherent Member

UDD - Université du Domicile SAS UDD **Country: France**
www.iperia.eu

UDD is hosted by Iperia l'Institut, an association which has been contributing to the professionalization of domestic work for more than 20 years by providing training and certification. UDD works in the field of well-being and social innovation. UDD focuses on skills&home. UDD explores the invisible practices, activities, and skills, that are developed at home and that people do unconsciously. Living Lab's main goal is to offer value, and to co-create trainings, products, services and good practices, to give people solutions to benefit from all of them. This will also enable the professionalization of domestic abilities. The UDD has the capabilities to create user-centred solutions to help people to live better at home.

Adherent Member

Universcience Living Lab

Etablissement Public
Palais de la Découverte
Cité des sciences et de
l'industrie

Country: France
www.cite-sciences.fr

Universcience merges two Parisian science centres: i) the “Palais de la Découverte”; and ii) “la Cité des sciences et de l’industrie”. Its simple yet challenging goal is to inspire as many people as possible to be curious about the world around them, encouraging them both to marvel at science and to engage in scientific reasoning. Universcience provides: i) exhibitions accessible to all; ii) conferences, debates, events, publications; iii) spaces designed specifically for children (Cité des enfants); iv) dedicated services at the “Cité des métiers” and “Cité de la santé”; v) documentary resources with the Science Library; vi) experiments with innovative tools such as the FabLab and the Living Lab at the Carrefour numérique.

Universcience Living Lab welcomes and supports innovative projects in the fields of education, culture, entrepreneurship, social innovation and digital technologies. Visitors are involved as co-designers in the research or innovation process, influencing and bringing added value to the project.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban
- Other areas of work

Main Expertise

Innovation Strategies

Business Model Innovation

Participatory Tools & Methods

Stakeholder Management

Real-life Experimentation

Service Design

User & Living Lab Research

Living Labs in GERMANY

Innovation Partner

Collaborating Centre on Sustainable Consumption and Production

Collaborating Centre on Sustainable Consumption and Production

Country: Germany
www.cscp.org

The CSCP (Collaborating Centre on Sustainable Consumption and Production) is an international, non-profit think and do tank. Together with companies, political organisations and civil society actors, the CSCP pursues its mission to mainstream sustainability towards enabling the good life for all. The focus of the Centre is on enabling sustainable consumption and production patterns. With its collaborative approach, the CSCP accelerates change based on the special expertise of the Centre in the following areas: Lifestyles & Behaviour, Infrastructure, Products & Services, Business & Entrepreneurship and Policy. Within these areas, the centre works as a think and do tank, specialised in collaborating with diverse organisations around the globe and across sectors. Together they work on the vision of a good life by identifying, developing and scaling transformative solutions.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Mobility
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban
- Water (Blue Economy)
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization
- Other areas of work

Adherent Member

K8 Institut fuer strategische Aesthetik gGmbH

K8

Country: Germany
k8.design

As a “transformation organization”, K8 focuses on cross-sector involvement in processes of change. Transformation is understood as a combination of 5 fields of action. At the center of all transformation processes are people acting individually and collectively. K8 therefore explores and develops complementary forms of collective, public, data-based, value-creating and sustainable action. Each field of action can become the lead dimension (depending on the context), and the other focal points can then be used to identify concrete options for action. Because they focus on different social contexts, these fields of action also refer to complementary dimensions of social impact.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Health & Well Being
- Media
- Mobility
- Policies
- Regulatory Learning
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

Lab for social informatics

Heilbronn University

Country: Germany
www.hs-heilbronn.de

Description: The Lab for Social Informatics at Heilbronn University merges academic expertise, industry insights, and societal perspectives to drive gender-responsive innovation with a strong focus on inclusivity. Through its feminist living lab methodology, the lab employs co-creation, participatory research, and user-centered design to tackle social and technological issues—ranging from AI to digital inclusion. A multi-stakeholder governance model unites academic leaders, funders, civic organizations, municipalities, and tech companies, ensuring collaborative decisions and shared responsibility. The lab's interdisciplinary team includes researchers, project managers, designers, and community engagement specialists, all working to scale methods for societal impact. Equipped with mobile maker spaces, behavioural research facilities, and advanced data analysis tools, the Lab for Social Informatics conducts real-world experiments in diverse contexts, from startups to urban neighbourhoods. Funded largely by federal grants, the lab addresses gender inequality, ethical AI design, and broader innovation challenges.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Environment/Climate Change
- Gender
- Health & Well Being
- Mobility
- Research
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Water (Blue Economy)

Main Expertise

Participatory Tools & Methods Real-life Experimentation User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

Living Labs Incubator

RWTH Aachen University

Country: Germany
<https://www.humtec.rwth-aachen.de/cms/humtec/forschung/~mgveq/living-labs-incubator/?lidx=1>

Recognising the vital role of Living Labs in mission-driven, impact-oriented research, the Living Labs Incubator (LLI) supports and studies Living Labs affiliated with RWTH Aachen University, one of Germany's largest technical universities. The LLI pursues three core goals: (i) to build a network of existing and emerging Living Labs; (ii) to develop robust methods for Living Lab research and evaluation; and (iii) to establish a Living Lab Training Center that fosters transdisciplinary education and research.

Against the backdrop of global sustainability challenges and regional structural transformation, the LLI aims to strengthen the local, regional, and national innovation ecosystems in which RWTH Aachen plays a central role. By offering peer-learning formats, conceptual frameworks, and methodological guidance, the LLI enables critical reflection on both political and epistemic dimensions of Living Lab work.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Circular Economy
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Mobility
- Regulatory Learning
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban
- Water (Blue Economy),
- Zero pollution & decarbonization

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation Participatory Tools & Methods Governance Modelling Impact Assessments Implementation after Testing Innovation Strategies Policy Making

Scaling-up Stakeholder Management Living Lab Evaluation Real-life Experimentation Service Design User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

SmartFactoryOWL

Fraunhofer IOSB-INA

Country: Germany

www.smartfactory-owl.de

The SmartFactoryOWL is the real lab for industry 4.0 in Ostwestfalen-Lippe and offers companies and research institutions extensive possibilities and services for the co-creation of the factory of the future. The joint institution of the Fraunhofer IOSB-INA and the OWL University of Applied Sciences in Lemgo follows the three pillars: research, qualification, and transfer of technologies of the digital industry. In these three fields, SmartFactoryOWL provides answers to many questions and inspiration for your own development, demonstrating it in a worldwide unique Industry 4.0 infrastructure. What do you find there? On highly attractive research, production, and seminar areas, SmartFactoryOWL informs you about research results in the areas of digital transformation of the industry, future of work and process optimization. On 2000 sqm production and innovation area, technologies are presented in a way that you can experience their benefits first hand. SmartFactoryOWL helps companies to identify fields of action in the transfer of knowledge and technology and in the implementation of projects by matching them with experts in a suitable way.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Circular Economy
- Energy
- Industries & Manufacturing
- SME & Start-ups

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation

Participatory Tools & Methods

Impact Assessments

Implementation after Testing

Innovation Strategies

Stakeholder Management

Living Lab Evaluation

User & Living Lab Research

Real-life Experimentation

Living Labs in GREECE

Adherent Member

CO2 Solution Living Lab Interbalkan Environment Centre **Country: Greece**
<https://www.linkedin.com/company/104654496/>

The CO2-Solutions Living Lab under Interbalkan Environment Center - Green Innovation Hub (I-BEC), brings together academia, industry, government, and civil society to address real-world environmental challenges and co-create innovative solutions focusing on advancing carbon farming practices to effectively reduce the carbon footprint and increase carbon sequestration. The CO2-Solutions Living Lab brings together diverse stakeholders to co-create practical solutions, promoting nature-based approaches, carbon farming, and precision agriculture. It builds networks, raises awareness, and showcases impact through national pilot stations applying carbon farming practices.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Environment/Climate Change
- Soil

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

Innovative Systems for Sustainable Development & Action Living Lab (ISSIDA-LL) Athina-Erevnitiko Kentro Kainotomias Stis Technologies Tis Pliroforias, Ton Epikoinonion Kai Tis Gnosis **Country: Greece**
<https://issida-ll.athenarc.gr>

Innovative Systems for Sustainable Development & Action Living Lab (ISSIDA-LL) provides services throughout the innovation cycle, including ideation, prototyping, testing, and implementation, which is based on the Design Thinking Models, combining a unique expertise in social and environmental sciences, engineering, and ICT. It provides tools and frameworks supporting sustainability, digital transformation, and systemic transitions toward green and inclusive growth. ISSIDA-LL services are also offered to other Living Labs, enabling and supporting them to invent, ideate and pilot solutions related to sustainable transformation.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Gender
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Soil
- Urban
- Water
- Zero Pollution
- Other areas of work

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

Internet of Food Alliance (INOFA)

INTERNET OF FOOD ALLIANCE SUPPORT OFFICE IKE

Country: Greece
<https://inofa.gr/>

Founded in 2022, INOFA operates on the premise that Digital Technology will dominate the European agrifood value chain. A vertically integrated cluster, initially funded by the Greek General Secretariat for Research and Innovation, it has been formed around an IoT connectivity framework encompassing telecommunications, cloud services, and remote agronomic consultancy. This cluster comprises farmers, packers, retailers, service providers, technology firms, RTOs, and civil society groups. Geographically spanning Greece, it covers animal farming and plan cultivation, as well as services. Aligned with the EU's Green Deal policy and member entities' practical needs, INOFA designs eco-conscious projects, supplying tools like GPS animal trackers and biostimulants. Additionally, digital traceability uplifts farmers' visibility, aiding successful transitions.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Rural
- Soil

Main Expertise

 Policy Making						
 User & Living Lab Research						

Accepted to Grow

Just Transition Living Lab

University of Western Macedonia

Country: Greece
<https://www.uowm.gr/>

“Just Transition” is an ecosystem sharing the same vision and implementing a process, based on structured and constructive dialogue and an agenda shared with citizens, workers, industry, enterprises, governments and academia, that need to be further elaborated and explored in geographical, economic, political, cultural, and social context. JTLL is an educational, collaborative, research and innovation living lab, created as a public-private partnership to tackle the Just Transition challenges at the respective areas around the globe. The Just Transition Institute Greece (JTIG), together with the University of Western Macedonia (UoWM), as well as other institutions adopting our dream for a just future, connect citizens, enterprises and policy makers of areas in transition, who face the greatest challenges of their modern history in our area.”

Accepted to Grow

KAEM Living Lab American Farm School – Innovation and Impact HUB **Country: Greece** www.afs.edu.gr

KAEM LL highlights the deep connection between olive trees, olive oil and environmental sustainability and cultural heritage. Educating consumers about their purchases and promoting responsible consumption is a key objective. It also aims to develop olive tourism and gastronomy as high-value offerings, marketing olive products as premium goods. Navigating legal frameworks, health assertions, and certifications, it ensures compliance and trust in olive products. A holistic, olive-centric system is proposed, integrating all aspects of olive production and consumption. The educational component focuses on fostering skills development and entrepreneurship within the olive industry, as well as improving transportation and processing techniques to enhance efficiency and product quality. This comprehensive approach aims to create a sustainable, culturally rich, and economically viable olive industry.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Environment/Climate Change
- Rural

Main Expertise

Participatory Tools & Methods, Governance Modelling, Impact Assessments, Implementation after Testing, Innovation Strategies, Scaling-up, Stakeholder Management, Living Lab Evaluation, Panel Management, Real-life Experimentation, Service Design

Adherent Member

Mediterranean Soil Living Lab (MACCSOIL) Mediterranean Agrofood Competence Center **Country: Greece** <https://macc.gr/en/macc-soil/>

The Mediterranean Soil Living Lab (MACCSOIL LL) embodies a visionary quest towards redefining the future of agriculture through the prism of soil sustainability. MACCSOILL LL invites living labs, Scientists and Communities, worldwide to join in a groundbreaking journey to unearth sustainable practices that safeguard our planet’s very foundation, its - soil. This dynamic platform it’s a movement towards harmonizing agricultural productivity with environmental stewardship. Through fostering a vibrant community of researchers, farmers, and eco-conscious innovators, MACC Soil LL is crafting a narrative where soil health is central to address global challenges of climate change and food security. It’s an open invitation for living labs globally to collaborate, share insights, and co-create solutions that resonate with the urgent need for sustainability. At the heart of the MACC Soil LL mission lies an inspiring vision: to transform soil into a living testament of resilience and prosperity.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Regulatory Learning
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Urban

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation, Participatory Tools & Methods, Governance Modelling, Impact Assessments, Implementation after Testing, Innovation Strategies, Policy Making, Scaling-up, Stakeholder Management, Living Lab Evaluation, Panel Management, Real-life Experimentation, Service Design, User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

SMART Living Lab

University of Western Macedonia (UOWM),
Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering

Country: Greece

<https://smart.ece.uowm.gr>

SMART is a Living Lab (LL) designed to act as a user-centric open innovation ecosystem attached to the value potential of new markets. The facilities of University of Western Macedonia and residential prosumers in the district of Central and Western Macedonia in Greece compose the real testing environment. SMART aims to balance the public action considering the generality of citizens' concern through the active participation of users. The different climate conditions and geographical particularities of the users allow a wide range of real-life testing, including actors with little economic weight. The team of SMART LL, consisting of Professors, post-doc researchers, PhD candidates and engineers, aims to create strong ties between the academia and the local business infrastructure with special focus on SMEs. SMART is based on the pillars of research, education and industrial testing. Through the educational dimension, the students can have access to records and assets of actual users.

Areas of work

- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Research
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

Effective Member

Thessaloniki Action for HeAlth & Wellbeing Living Lab

Medical Physics & Digital Innovation Lab
- School of Medicine,
Aristotle University of Thessaloniki

Country: Greece

<https://thessahall.com/>

The Thessaloniki Action for HeAlth & Wellbeing Living Lab (Thess-AHALL) - previously Thessaloniki Active & Healthy Ageing Living Lab, operational since 2014, is a unique research and innovation setting in the City of Thessaloniki, Region of Central Macedonia (Northern Greece). The living lab fosters initiatives encouraging regional development and sustainability of novel technologies in the Health & Wellbeing domain, focusing on the physical, mental, as well as social health, the Active & Healthy Ageing (AHA) and the enhancement of the Quality of Life. The Thess-AHALL is actively pursuing co-creation and co-design of technological solutions to improve health and social conditions for older adults, chronic patients & other vulnerable populations and facilitate independent living, as well as to up-skill and empower the current and future healthcare workforce.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors),
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Media
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Effective Member

Thessaloniki Smart Mobility Living Lab

Centre for Research and Technology Hellas - Hellenic Institute of Transport (CERTH - HIT)

Country: Greece
www.smartmlab.imet.gr

Thessaloniki Smart Mobility Living Lab is one of Europe's largest Living Labs on mobility. The entire city of Thessaloniki is a platform for testing technological and innovative solutions for shared and on-demand mobility, cooperative and autonomous vehicles and will soon be extended to freight transport. Thessaloniki is in the list of smart cities in the mobility sector, and this would not have been possible without the involvement of the bodies that make up the ecosystem of the city, which has been created over the last decade and is constantly growing. In this ecosystem, various mobility operators and technology providers are engaged in providing data and expertise to create the right conditions for the exploitation of this infrastructure for the benefit of the whole ecosystem, which has the citizens at its center. The Thessaloniki Smart Mobility Living Lab includes, among others: i) extended IoT equipment in vehicles (bikes, e-scooters, taxis and trains) and in the city streets (Bluetooth detectors, cameras, radars); ii) real time traffic data in the whole Region of Central Macedonia (including travel time along pre-defined routes and traffic speed in road segments); iii) short-term predictions of traffic conditions and travel time based on multi-source data; iv) mobility and activity patterns extraction and analysis.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Environment/Climate Change
- Mobility
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation

Participatory Tools & Methods

Governance Modelling

Impact Assessments

Implementation after Testing

Innovation Strategies

Policy Making

Scaling-up

Stakeholder Management

Living Lab Evaluation

Panel Management

Real-life Experimentation

Service Design

User & Living Lab Research

Living Labs in HONG KONG

Adherent Member

Living Lab in Gerontechnology for Age-Friendly Home

Housing Society Elderly Resources Centre

Country: Hong Kong
erc.hkhselderly.com/

Established in 2022 under the Hong Kong Housing Society Elderly Resources Centre (ERC), the Living Lab in Gerontechnology for Age-Friendly Home (AFHLL) functions as both a participatory design process and a real-home testing environment dedicated to advancing innovation in age-friendly living.

As a design process, AFHLL actively involves older adults as co-designers. By experiencing emerging age-friendly home products and offering direct feedback, they help developers refine solutions to better meet real-life needs.

At the heart of AFHLL is a fully equipped, simulated home environment located at ERC, where older adults interact with home product prototypes in a realistic setting. This space serves as a testbed for evaluation and supports user-centred innovation.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Health & Well Being
- Mobility
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Living Labs in HUNGARY

Adherent Member

Discovery Agricultural On-farm and Research Living Lab

Discovery Center Nonprofit Ltd.

Country: Hungary
<https://discoverycenter.eu/>

Discovery Living Lab has been operating since 2019 as a rural agriculture on-farm living lab - now one of Hungary's first agroecology-certified living labs, with a mission to advance participatory soil health management, precision agriculture, and agroecological transition across the Carpathian Basin. As a full member of both ENoLL and the EU Agroecology Partnership, we coordinate real-life experiments on thousands of hectares in collaboration with farmers, advisors, researchers, and municipalities. Our work spans cover crop innovation, mycorrhizal fungi monitoring, low-input farming systems, and farmer co-designed field trials. Discovery LL is financially independent and deeply embedded in national and international networks, including the HuMUS EU project and various regional soil initiatives. With a multidisciplinary team and established stakeholder base, we translate scientific evidence into practical outcomes and policy recommendations. We engage local actors through co-creation, living lab methodologies, and training formats tailored to Hungary's diverse soil types and climate stressors. Our goal is to become a key regional hub for resilient land use, system innovation, and inclusive knowledge co-production.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Rural

Main Expertise

 Scaling-up						
 User & Living Lab Research						

Adherent Member

Grow Stars Institute Living Lab

Csillagváros Kft.

Country: Hungary
<https://www.csillagvaros.com/>

Csillagváros Kft is operates by 6 years a vertical farm where industrial production, energy reduction focused trials and several other experiments are conducted. By far, the Company also dealing with Space Agriculture by sending seeds to Space and using them for research, breeding and education.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Urban

Main Expertise

 Living Lab Evaluation						
 User & Living Lab Research						

Effective Member

ÖMKi On-farm Living Lab

Hungarian Research Institute of Organic Agriculture

Country: Hungary
www.biokutatas.hu

ÖMKi On-farm Living Lab is an agroecology-focused nationwide participatory experimentation network which includes a variety of field trials and technology tests co-designed and co-implemented with farmers and other stakeholders of the value chain in Hungary, with the aim to promote agroecological transition. We work since 2012 in the field of arable crops, horticulture, viticulture, and since 2020 also animal husbandry. In frame of the On-farm Living Lab, we test in different sub-networks how new products, practices and technological innovations perform under the diversity of everyday farming. Participating farmers gain feedback directly from their own production experiences, land, and technology creating space for open innovation and dynamic knowledge co-creation between farmers, researchers, advisors and other stakeholders. At the same time, the results give a broader picture of Hungarian organic and agroecological production practices and locally applicable solutions.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Soil

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

Well-being Living Lab Nagykövácsi

TREBAG Intellectual property- and Project Manager Ltd

Country: Hungary
www.trebag.hu

The mission of the Well-being Living Lab Nagykövácsi is to carry out and participate in R&D activities that can be used to improve people's well-being and quality of life in many areas of life. Its mission is to develop, deliver, apply and disseminate new services and methods (e.g. through education) using the results of R&D activities.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Rural
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Living Labs in INDIA

Adherent Member

**Green Urban Mobility
Innovation Living Lab
(GUMILL)**

Indian Institute of
Science (IISc)

Country: India
www.giz.de

The Green Urban Mobility Innovation Living Lab (GUMILL) in India is a collaborative platform dedicated to sustainable and inclusive urban mobility. Now housed at the Indian Institute of Science, it brings together communities, stakeholders, and public–private partnerships to co-create solutions that improve first- and last-mile connectivity, active mobility, and public transport accessibility, with a focus on vulnerable groups. By combining global peer learning with local pilot projects—such as shared electric mobility services and integration of non-motorized transport—GUMILL is building institutional capacity to test, scale, and replicate community-driven innovations for emerging urban environments.

Areas of work

- Mobility
- Urban

Main Expertise

Participatory
Tools &
Methods

Implementation
after Testing

Innovation
Strategies

Stakeholder
Management

Real-life
Experimentation

Living Labs in IRELAND

Adherent Member

Atlantic Innovation Region

Western Development Commission

Country: Ireland

www.westerndevelopment.ie

The WDC’s remit covers the seven counties primarily on the Atlantic coast of Ireland: Donegal, Leitrim, Sligo, Roscommon, Mayo, Galway, and Clare. Its strategic themes for 2019-2024 are: i) Regional Promotion, ii) Regional Leadership, and iii) Sustainable Enterprise. The WDC’s role is that of an Orchestrator that enables this region to stimulate new social/business, innovations, partnerships, initiate experiments, and Living Labs, and foster a vibrant ecosystem across the region with global links and recognition. The most important characteristic of the AIR Living lab is the network it creates for multiple actors to come together to test innovative solutions to societal problems. Using a quadruple helix approach, the Lab acts as an orchestrator to bring together cross-cutting competencies in creativity, data, sensors, and mobility to tackle emerging challenges in vertical industries such as healthcare, energy generation, and transport. Network allows the actors to work with industry, Academia and civic society in a way that combines local knowledge and sectoral expertise to identify challenges and to source partners to solve these challenges. The Lab is also linked to the WDC Investment Fund, providing a path to scaling for successful start-up ideas that emerge from experiments.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Energy
- Health & Well Being
- Mobility
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation

Participatory Tools & Methods

Governance Modelling

Innovation Strategies

Policy Making

Stakeholder Management

Living Lab Evaluation

User & Living Lab Research

Real-life Experimentation

Effective Member

Citizen Innovation Lab University of Limerick & Limerick City & County Council
Country: Ireland
<https://citizeninnovationlab.ie/>

Limerick’s Citizen Innovation Lab is a place for observation, co-creation and experimentation in the city. It is a collaboration between the University of Limerick, Limerick City and County Council, and the citizens of Limerick, supporting them to work together on a sustainable future for the city. It is a place where people can help shape a path to a climate neutral Limerick by 2050. As a living lab, it leads and supports collaborative research projects, citizen-led initiatives, digital and citizen science tools, and public engagement activities. The shared approach focuses on areas including decarbonisation, the clean energy transition, climate innovation, digitisation and technology, active travel, and urban development. The Citizen Innovation Lab puts people at the heart of Limerick’s climate transition.

Areas of work

- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Mobility
- Policies
- Regulatory Learning
- Research
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

 Stakeholder Management						
 User & Living Lab Research						

Adherent Member

Dingle Peninsula MOL TEIC
Country: Ireland
www.dinglehub.com

The vision of Dingle Hub is to build a creative, liveable, and sustainable community, fostering a vibrant and diverse ecosystem of stakeholders to facilitate the creation and maintenance of well-paid, year-round incomes on the Dingle Peninsula. Dingle Peninsula Living Lab has developed an innovative model of Remote Regional Development. It balances highly structured focus, anchored in core pillars, with a flexibility of delivery across processes and partnerships. It builds on existing assets and continuously shares outputs and learnings. Dingle Peninsula Living Lab applies a flexible multi-layered approach building on the local; attracting the new, building networks of resources and capabilities aspiring to, primed for and delivering entrepreneurial growth of sustainable enterprise (private and social). Engagement at all levels – community, research, industry, and policymaker – is central to this story and has led to a hybrid top-down meets bottom-up approach that is achieving concrete results and providing value for all stakeholders.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Mobility
- Rural
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

 Living Lab Evaluation						
 User & Living Lab Research						

Living Labs in ISRAEL

Adherent Member

Cityzone	ATIDIM HIGH TECH INDUSTRIAL PARK LTD	Country: Israel https://www.city-zone.co/
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CityZone is a smart city innovation hub and urban living lab in Tel Aviv, created by the Municipality, Tel Aviv University, and Atidim Park. Since 2019, it has supported startups in designing, testing, and validating solutions in a real-world urban sandbox, with direct access to municipal systems, academic expertise, and global networks. Combining hands-on experimentation with mentorship and strategic guidance, CityZone bridges innovation and implementation, fostering scalable solutions that drive smarter, more sustainable, and citizen-focused cities.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Circular Economy
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Mobility
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Urban
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation

Participatory Tools & Methods

Impact Assessments

Implementation after Testing

Innovation Strategies

Living Lab Evaluation

Scaling-up

User & Living Lab Research

Accepted to Grow

Homecare Innovation Technologies Lab (HIT-Lab)

Holon Institute of Technology

Country: Israel
<https://www.hit.ac.il>

HIT-Lab focuses on homecare technologies and: (i) supports stakeholders with solutions in real life setting starting from clinical partner’s needs, to co-create and innovative solutions providing MVP for clinical trials and implementation healthcare setting; (ii) addresses the growth of the data challenge: as more Patient Generated- Data (PGD) are collected they develop tools and methodologies for collecting, managing and integrating PGD with EHR (Electronic-Health-Record) data; (iii) is connected in a satellite structure to labs with complementary expertise in data science, bio-medical engineering , AI-based applications, with multidisciplinary teams to address needs from idea to implementation; (iv) has courses in which students join multidisciplinary teams addressing homecare challenges. There is a training program of 6-months for physicians in their medical training (in collaboration with IMA -Israeli Medical Association) educating them to co-creation and multidisciplinary R&D.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Health & Well Being

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation

Participatory Tools & Methods

Implementation after Testing

Innovation Strategies

Scaling-up

Stakeholder Management

Panel Management

Service Design

Real-life Experimentation

User & Living Lab Research

Living Labs in ITALY

Adherent Member

City of the future Living Lab San Raffaele Hospital

Country: Italy
www.hsr.it

San Raffaele Scientific Institute's City of the Future Living Lab in Milan has been created to observe an extended number of users interacting with a great number of services within a real city environment, as well as to engage them in a co-creation process that triggers and helps flourish tomorrow's e-Services.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Health & Well Being
- Smart Cities & Regions

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation

Participatory Tools & Methods

Implementation after Testing

Innovation Strategies

Scaling-up

Stakeholder Management

Living Lab Evaluation

Panel Management

Real-life Experimentation

Service Design

User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

Green Schools Living Lab Provincia di Treviso

Country: Italy
www.trevisoscuole.it

The Living Lab Green Schools of the Province of Treviso aims at changing users' behaviour to foster energy saving. To achieve this goal Green Schools uses the management of the school building as a model in which the user/student/teacher can actively participate thanks to the IT tools used for the managing activities, which are accessible through a web portal (www.trevisoscuole.it). Thus, Green Schools is an answer to the need of reducing the costs for managing buildings through a reduction of energy consumption and through a rational and conscious use of the common good. Green Schools furtherly provides an important educational added value as activities aiming at energy saving and sustainability are mainly addressed to, and performed by, students and teachers. The main characteristics of Green Schools Living Lab are: i) users themselves, as well as technology, become a real "tool" for energy saving; ii) in the Green Schools Living Lab the roles of technology and users are complementary; iii) technology is the lever through which users are stimulated towards a virtuous behaviour and users efficiency can boost new technological investments on energy efficiency, creating a virtuous circle; iv) it has a spill over effect in the social context, in informal learning, in the technological field and in the economic field.

Areas of work

- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change

Main Expertise

Participatory Tools & Methods

Stakeholder Management

Living Lab Evaluation

Panel Management

Real-life Experimentation

Adherent Member

InnovAALab - Apulian Living Lab on “Healthy, Active & Assisted Living”

National Research Council of Italy

Country: Italy

InnovAALab - the Apulian Living Lab on “Healthy, Active & Assisted Living” - was born as a part of the Strategic Plan and Vision of the activities of the Public-Private Partnership “INNOVAAL” (according the PPPP model), funded by the Ministry of Research in Italy in the field of Ambient Assisted Living (AAL), Independent Living, Ageing Well, Healthy Living, and related development of Products and Services. InnovAALab covers a large area at territorial level involving also the additional actors coming from the regional projects funded in the frame of “Health, Wellness and Socio-Cultural Dynamics” of the Apulian ICT Living Labs initiative.

Areas of work

- Health & Well Being
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Accepted to Grow

Innovative and sustainable models for soil health

ERSAF

Country: Italy

<https://www.ersaf.lombardia.it/agricoltura/living-lab-suolo/>

The Living Lab (LL) “Innovative and sustainable models for soil health” was founded in May 2022 with the overall objective to calibrate and introduce sustainable practices of agro-ecosystem management within intensively managed agricultural lands of the Po Valley, as well as monitor, report, and verify the performances towards healthy agricultural soils and carbon farming strategies. This goal is achieved by supporting a multiactor approach with the concomitant involvement of farmers, researchers, experts, and other stakeholders directly engaged in the activities of the LL, especially focused on the development of innovative and sustainable soil management models, associated with preservation and increase of soil organic carbon content in connection with EU MISSION “A Soil Deal for Europe” objectives related to Carbon Farming and on the resources management.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Circular Economy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Rural
- Soil
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

KLIOLab - Knowledge-based Lifecycle InnOvation Laboratory

DHITECH (Distretto High Tech) **Country: Italy**

KLIOLab represents a synergic partnership among public and private actors aimed at developing innovative ICT solutions for the aeronautic and mechanical industries through knowledge, practices and resource sharing and the creation of start-ups and spin-offs. KLIOLab has been created in 2014 by formalizing cooperative practices built through long-term cooperation among public and private partners of the DHITECH (Distretto High Tech), the Apulian district for high technology development, hosting organisation for the KLIOLab. Currently this partnership, composed of aeronautic industries, universities, high-competent spin-offs in the ICT industry, Public Administrations and students, is committed to the implementation and deployment of a methodological framework moving the product life cycle management from an enterprise-based view to a value network-based view. The main business line of KLIOLab embodies executing innovation projects, through public and private funds, and the involvement of different categories of users in the innovation process.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Mobility
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Adherent Member

Living Lab for Oceans and Water (CNR)

National Research Council of Italy (CNR) - Department Earth system science and environmental technologies

Country: Italy

The Living Lab for Ocean and Waters focuses on co-creating sustainable, science-based solutions for water and environmental challenges. It operates trying to address climate change, water resource management, and ecosystem restoration. This LL has strong expertise in environmental monitoring, digital tools, and participatory governance, supporting hands-on experimentation in river basins and coastal zones.

Adherent Member

Lunigiana Amica XR8 di Molinari
Francesco & C. sas **Country: Italy**
Rural Living Lab

Lunigiana Amica is a non-profit association born from the needs of local agricultural producers to promote their products through a short-range supply chain. Lunigiana Amica’s goal is to connect and network the main actors of the agri-food system, setting up product marketing strategies within and outside the territory of Massa-Carrara province. The ultimate goal is to achieve positive effects for the members of the association and for the Lunigiana area. The association was born in 2007 and promoted by Coldiretti, CIA, Confcooperative, and the Municipality of Licciana Nardi.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Rural

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Participatory Tools & Methods	Governance Modelling	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Policy Making
Scaling-up	Stakeholder Management	Living Lab Evaluation	Panel Management	Real-life Experimentation	Service Design	User & Living Lab Research

Effective Member

Mediterranean Innovation Rural Living Lab (MEDIL) CIHEAM Bari **Country: Italy**
www.iamb.it

The Mediterranean Innovation Rural Living Lab aims to become a catalyst for innovation ecosystems promoting the sustainable development of rural and coastal areas in Apulia and the Mediterranean region. The lab’s objectives include:

- Spreading the culture of Open-Innovation through the development of training courses, research, knowledge transfer, and international cooperation in the Mediterranean Area.
- Creating a multi-actor network that applies a systematic approach of co-creation, integrating research and innovation processes in communities and real-life environments.
- Generating innovation by supporting youth entrepreneurship and facilitating the co-design and acceleration of solutions for businesses, rural, and coastal communities.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Water (Blue Economy)

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Participatory Tools & Methods	Governance Modelling	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Scaling-up	Stakeholder Management
Panel Management	Real-life Experimentation	Service Design	User & Living Lab Research			

Adherent Member

Puglia Smart Lab

DHITECH (Distretto High Tech)

Country: Italy

www.pugliasmartlab.dhitech.it

The Smart Community around Puglia Smart LL plays a fundamental role toward an holistic view aimed to understand the processes of change in the social, economic and organization contexts and to achieve an harmonious progression in the society, by listening to all the stakeholder in the territory. This approach already started, promotes the collaboration of citizens with all the stakeholders involved in service delivering. The “smart” use of new technologies, defined in Puglia@Service project to be used and tested within the Lab, enables service integration overcoming silos structure of the services, nowadays strictly divides between public and private. For this reason Puglia Smart LL aims to put in practise a radical change in delivery services for a territory, oriented to become a smart community. Puglia Smart LL is developed within the area of the “Internet-based Service Engineering”, devoted to the research of scientific analytical methodologies for the design, production and deployment of innovative services. Moreover it is positioned between Service Science and open innovation. The innovative characteristics of the LL are: i) a pervasive technological infrastructure, thought to act as the nervous system of the “smart territory”; ii) a qualified human capital, developed according to the profile of the “Innovator and Entrepreneur Engineer”, able to create economic and social value (Technological Entrepreneurship); iii) start-up specialized in the Service Engineering Area, able to facilitate the development of “technology-based” innovative services.

Accepted to Grow

Roma Smart City Lab

Roma Capitale

Country: Italy

<https://www.labsmartcityroma.it/>

A place for discussion between the Capitoline Administration and the Citizens on the issues of Innovation applied to the City.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Media
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

Santa Chiara Lab University of Siena **Country: Italy**
<https://santachiaralab.unisi.it/it>

Santa Chiara Lab is the innovation centre of the University of Siena. It is a place that catalyzes many cultural and social initiatives involving many actors (organizations, institutions, companies, Associations of the territory, students, and researchers) who see in the Santa Chiara Lab a place of knowledge exchange and permanent contamination. Santa Chiara Lab collaborates with citizens, universities, companies, cities and regions for joint value co-creation and co-design, rapid prototyping, experimenting and demonstrating concrete solutions to foster innovation, whilst supporting the transition from fundamental to applied research, in several domains such as sustainability, agrifood, public health, education, and digitalization.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Rural
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization
- Other areas of work

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation, Participatory Tools & Methods, Governance Modelling, Impact Assessments, Innovation Strategies, Scaling-up, Stakeholder Management, Living Lab Evaluation, Panel Management, Real-life Experimentation, Service Design, User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

Thriving Entrepreneurial and Creative Lab (TECLA) EIS - Easy integrazione di sistemi s.r.l. **Country: Italy**
www.easyint.it

The Thriving Entrepreneurial and Creative Lab (TECLA) is an initiative that intends to exploit the potential of the Palermo city to become thriving and sustainable by leveraging and reinforcing the entrepreneurial and innovative capacity of local actors in the creative industry field. TECLA is a physical space that encourages participants to discuss ideas and projects, meet partners, and develop collaborative methodologies so that sustainable development goals can be supported by new technologies and advanced multimedia tools, as well as by knowledge in the social sciences, art and humanities. TECLA is managed by EIS, a private innovation management company and it is part of the creative hub CRE.ZI. PLUS, hosted in the cultural campus of the Palermo Municipality “Cantieri Culturali alla Zisa”. It capitalises the results of EU funded projects, and it is part of the Euro-Mediterranean network of U-SOLVE urban innovation hubs. TECLA has been building a diverse ecosystem of local and international enterprises active in different creative domains, which are engaged in joint projects and initiatives. TECLA’s activities also attract policy makers, academics, industry professionals, designers, manufacturers and other key actors in the urban community.

Areas of work

- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation, Participatory Tools & Methods, Impact Assessments, Implementation after Testing, Innovation Strategies, Scaling-up, Stakeholder Management, Service Design

Adherent Member

TIE-LL Technology Innovation Ecosystem

Apulian High Tech District

Country: Italy
www.dhitech.it

TIE Living Lab is hosted by DHITECH and stems from the research project VINCENTE (Virtual collective INtelligentE ENvironment to develop sustainable Technology Entrepreneurship ecosystem), co-funded by the Italian Ministry of Education, University and Research. The TIE Living Lab’s mission is to conceive and promote, openly and collaboratively, a personalizable ecosystem of actors and stakeholders, relationships and resources, actions and initiatives to support potential entrepreneurs and companies in cultivating innovative ideas and entrepreneurial projects as well as developing entrepreneurial competencies and attitudes. By favouring the arising of ideas and the exchange of knowledge and experiences, TIE Living Lab enables the open dialogue among scientists, researchers, companies, entrepreneurs and investors, citizen and associations, local authorities, universities and public institutions to jointly conceive, design, and realize innovative solutions and entrepreneurial projects. ness of the region itself.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Mobility
- Research
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Innovation Strategies

Stakeholder Management

Business Model Innovation

User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

Torino City Lab

Comune di Torino

Country: Italy
www.torinocitylab.it

Torino City Lab (TCL) is a real-life urban laboratory open to all companies interested in testing innovative solutions of public interest in Turin. Specific challenges and priority areas are periodically identified, enabling the launch of dedicated thematic laboratories.

Launched in 2018 by the City of Turin, TCL is an always open platform designed to create simplified conditions for companies and startups to test innovative solutions in real urban environments. Today, the initiative counts around 90 national and international partners.

Since 2021, thanks to the House of Emerging Technologies of Turin – CTE NEXT has expanded its mission to include start-up acceleration and technology transfer. Its focus is on emerging technologies enabled by 5G, with particular attention to strategic sectors such as land and air mobility, Industry 4.0, and Smart City solutions.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Circular Economy
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Mobility
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation

Participatory Tools & Methods

Governance Modelling

Impact Assessments

Implementation after Testing

Innovation Strategies

Policy Making

Scaling-up

Stakeholder Management

Living Lab Evaluation

Panel Management

Real-life Experimentation

Service Design

User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

EDUTECH STEAM Lab Klaipėda University

Country: Lithuania

<https://shmf.ku.lt/struktura/laboratorijos/edutech-steam-laboratorija>

The EDUTECH STEAM Laboratory at Klaipėda University is an open, user-centered innovation ecosystem that connects teachers, students, researchers, and EdTech developers to co-create and test educational tools in real-life learning environments. Focusing on project-based STEAM education, digital learning, and AI integration, it equips future educators with digital, professional, and innovation leadership skills. Through collaboration with academic, school, and social partners, prospective teachers help design and adopt transformative practices, strengthening the university's long-standing expertise in teacher education within the EU-CONEXUS alliance.

Areas of work

- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Participatory Tools & Methods

Impact Assessments

Innovation Strategies

Policy Making

Real-life Experimentation

User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

LIRA lab - Living Innovations for Regional Advancement

Lithuanian Centre for Social Sciences; Institute of Economics and Rural Development

Country: Lithuania
<https://www.ekvi.lt/en/lira-lab>

LIRA Lab – Living Innovations for Regional Advancement is a Living Lab dedicated to strengthening regional innovation ecosystems through interdisciplinary collaboration, AI-based stakeholder modeling, and the practical application of research in economics and management. Named after the lyre, symbolizing harmony and balance, LIRA aims to support socially and economically balanced transformation. As a diagnostic and co-creation space, the lab connects academia, government, business, and citizens to explore and transfer the value of innovation. By aligning with international Living Lab standards, LIRA ensures quality, relevance, and impact in advancing research-driven solutions tailored to real-world challenges.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Circular Economy
- Rural
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Other areas of work

Main Expertise

 Policy Making						
 User & Living Lab Research						

Living Labs in MAURITIUS

Adherent Member

**Innovative Learning
& Teacher Education
Living Lab (IL.TE.LL)**

University of Mauritius

Country: Mauritius
www.uom.ac.mu

Innovative Learning & Teacher Education Living Lab (IL.TE.LL) is based on a multiple-impact social partnership (MISP) model and is essentially an integration of the Research and Development model that has governed LL's applied research activities in education technology, and a community engagement model when members involved in the Living Lab established a non-governmental organisation through an entity called Helping Our People. It is based on Whitehead's education research philosophy for social change through action research and the Living lab paradigm for Teaching and Learning. The MISP model fits in the 4P innovation framework where the Public sector is represented by the University, the Private Sector is represented by Microsoft Indian Ocean and French Pacific, with the People being academics, educators, and Youth volunteers (students). The beneficiaries and the partnerships among these actors are mediated through a collective social movement called Helping Our People. The Research and Development Model (Cycle 1) is based on a practitioner-oriented concept where research and development essentially become the drivers for practice-oriented enquiries to improve teaching and learning systems. It aims at field experimentation to test new practices, which are then formalized into teaching methods that can be cascaded down to educators for classroom application.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Education and/or Vocational Training

Main Expertise

Innovation
Strategies

Implementation
after Testing

Business
Model
Innovation

Policy
Making

Scaling-up

Real-life
Experimentation

Stakeholder
Management

Living Labs in **MONTENEGRO**

Adherent Member

ADP Zid Living Lab

Community Impact Accelerator - Zid

Country: Montenegro

www.zid.org.me

Community Impact Accelerator – Zid was establish ADP-Zid Living lab three years ago. But, throughout our 9-year experience in implementation of co-creative methodologies, we have adopted and practiced Living Lab principles to foster innovation in the Montenegrin community and to tackle societal challenges. As an accelerator, ADP-Zid supports and creates community transformation sollutions, which are based on connecting actors, innovative methodologies, research and technology transfer. The Accelerator organizes its work through three sectors: - Technology Transfer and Innovation Development Centre, which comprises of several supporting units – Living lab, Research Centre and I2 Maker Space; - Solidary Economy and Entrepreneurship Development sector, within which the Community Support Business Cluster functions; and - Resource Centre for Active Participation.

Areas of work

- Circular Economy
- Energy
- Mobility
- Policies
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Governance Modelling

Participatory Tools & Methods

Policy Making

Stakeholder Management

Panel Management

User & Living Lab Research

Living Labs in NETHERLANDS

Adherent Member

Blue Hotspot Water, Soil and Climate Stichting Yuverta

Country: Netherlands
hotspotwaterbodemklimaat.nl

Collaboration with partners is essential for developing and implementing innovative, practice-oriented blue-green education focused on societal issues related to water, soil, and climate. This partnership must be sustainable, multi-year, and shared, involving partners who are willing to contribute, pioneer, and learn. The Blue Hotspot and regional hubs form the core of this approach, bringing together educational institutions, businesses, government, and citizens to work on current challenges through projects, research, and learning activities. The Blue Hotspot acts as a central community for co-creation and innovation, based on three pillars: education and learning, content development of blue-green education, and practice-oriented knowledge sharing. For each theme (water, soil, climate), a dedicated Hotspot is established, supported by regional hubs that coordinate implementation.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Soil
- Urban
- Water (Blue Economy)

Main Expertise

 Living Lab Evaluation					
 Real-life Experimentation					

Adherent Member

Care Innovation Center West-Brabant Care Innovation Center

Country: Netherlands
www.cic-westbrabant.nl

The Care Innovation Centre West Brabant is a foundation and network organization that contributes to the development and implementation of innovations by stimulating, connecting, and supporting healthcare- and welfare organizations, educational institutions, and businesses that contribute to innovation in healthcare. The Centre initiates projects that contribute to innovations, inspired by the concept of Positive Health, through the organisation of knowledge and inspiration sessions, arranging workshop series, initiating and supporting innovation projects, and launching training programs. By doing so, the Care Innovation Centre West Brabant contributes to prevention, sustainable care, increasing job satisfaction, and reducing workload. The Centre established sustainable collaborations with a core group of partners who endorse its vision and are committed to the same goals. We make innovation accessible by sharing knowledge, contacts, successes, and failures.

Areas of work

- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Health & Well Being
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

 Stakeholder Management						
 Service Design						

Innovation Partner

Delft University of Technology

Delft University of Technology (faculty of Technology, Policy and Management)

Country: Netherlands
<https://www.tudelft.nl/en/>

As a leading academic institution in the field of engineering, technology and innovation in the Netherlands, Delft University of Technology and its faculty members are engaged in cutting-edge research in innovation studies, sustainable development, governance, and decision-making, with a strong focus on user-centric and interdisciplinary collaborations. We house various labs and a number of research groups focused on fostering innovation. These include: the Design for Values Institute, which explores how technology can be designed and governed to align with human values; the Samelab, which develops serious games; and the Transdisciplinary Lab for Learning and Research, which tests, explores and reflects upon innovative co-creative processes to address scientific and societal challenges in research and education. These labs provide platforms for collaborative research, experimentation, and knowledge exchange, forming a research ecosystem oriented to technological innovation and learning.

Areas of work

- Circular Economy
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Mobility
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Soil
- Water (Blue Economy)

Effective Member

Eindhoven Living Lab

City of Eindhoven

Country: Netherlands
www.eindhoven.nl

Situated in the centre of the Brainport Eindhoven region, the city of Eindhoven has a strong commitment towards its citizens to enhance the quality of life, by mobilising the creative power of triple helix parties and citizens/end users all together. It is also opening the city itself as a real-life testing ground for products and services with an added value that meet the needs, ambitions and concerns of the end users. Bringing together partners on the one hand and creating/ contributing to structures in which partners can meet on the other hand are the two main points that are to characterise Eindhoven Living Lab, which is the umbrella approach to incorporate these Living Labs and future ones into one, more integrated and integral approach. Eindhoven Living Lab is about: i) Living Labs in which the City of Eindhoven is taking an active lead role; ii) Living Labs in which the City of Eindhoven is taking a minor role as a partner, or which are merely facilitated by the City by providing the necessary infrastructure and the access to it; in this case the Living Lab can extend beyond the territory of the city.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Mobility
- Regulatory Learning
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization
- Other areas of work

Main Expertise

Innovation Partner

South Holland Impact Alliance (ZHIA) Living Lab(s)

South Holland Impact Alliance

Country: Netherlands
<https://www.zhia.nl>

The Dutch society is facing a multitude of challenges, impending labour market shortages, rising healthcare costs, increasing health disparities, new security threats, and adaptation to climate change, requiring innovative approaches and contextual tackling. The four major Universities of Applied Sciences in South Holland, namely – The Hague University of Applied Sciences (THUAS), InHolland University of Applied Sciences (InHolland), Rotterdam University of Applied Sciences (RUAS), Leiden University of Applied Sciences (LUAS) established the South-Holland Impact Alliance (ZHIA). ZHIA has experience and expertise, thanks to the strong ties with stakeholders in the local neighbourhoods, the cities and the province itself. Netherlands recognizes the ZHIA as a powerful, recognizable knowledge and innovation network. ZHIA is recognizable in the areas of Health, Care, and Well-being, Sustainability, and AI and has actively contributed at reducing health disparities in the region.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Circular Economy
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation, Participatory Tools & Methods, Implementation after Testing, Innovation Strategies, Policy Making, Stakeholder Management, Living Lab Evaluation, Service Design, Real-life Experimentation, User & Living Lab Research

Effective Member

Urban Leisure & Tourism Lab

Inholland University of Applied Sciences

Country: Netherlands
<https://www.inholland.nl>

The Urban Leisure & Tourism Lab was founded by the Inholland University of Applied Sciences and it is based in Amsterdam and Rotterdam. It is at the forefront of addressing societal challenges through urban tourism, leading the way in shaping sustainable solutions for the future of the Leisure and Tourism industry.

The LL operates as a dynamic platform for (trans)disciplinary applied education and research, promoting collaboration across diverse domains of expertise and knowledge areas. This approach ensures projects are firmly grounded in the real world - yielding impactful research, innovative tools, thought leadership, and publications. Rooted in the community, the LL adopt a quintuple helix perspective - taking biodiversity into account, maintaining a longitudinal focus, and being committed to leaving a legacy through their interventions.

Areas of work

- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Health & Well Being
- Research
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation, Participatory Tools & Methods, Governance Modelling, Impact Assessments, Implementation after Testing, Innovation Strategies, Stakeholder Management, Living Lab Evaluation, Real-life Experimentation, User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

Urban Management - Fieldlabs

The Amsterdam
University of Applied
Sciences

Country: Netherlands
www.hva.nl

The Urban Management Fieldlabs are hosted by the Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences in collaboration with Amsterdam Municipality.

Urban Management Fieldlabs develop innovative approaches to metropolitan problems. Urban Management Fieldlabs were initiated in collaboration with stakeholders in three areas of the city: Nieuw-est, Zuidoost, and Oost. The Fieldlabs focus on developing area-based solutions to tangible urban challenges through co-creation. Together with local stakeholders, a shared long-term research and innovation agenda is formulated at the start of each Fieldlab. To ensure the focus on challenges that are specific to the areas in which the Fieldlabs are based, the local strategic development plan of the city district forms the starting point in developing this agenda. The UM Fieldlabs function as continuous learning environments focusing on the development of knowledge, but also on the improvement of practice through the direct application of acquired knowledge in tangible interventions. Because of the dynamic, complex and multi-faceted character of urban issues, addressing them will never be possible by only focusing on one aspect. The UM Fieldlabs are local innovation milieus aiming to contribute to the social innovation needed to address multi-scalar, multi-actor and multi-disciplinary urban challenges. A multi-disciplinary research team that is constituted based on the nature of the issue at hand is involved to ensure well informed decisions are made.

Effective Member

WaterCampus Leeuwarden

Municipality of
Leeuwarden

Country: Netherlands
www.leeuwarden.nl

At the WaterCampus Leeuwarden, innovations in the field of water technology are developed, tested, upscaled and introduced in the global market. The WaterCampus is a host to a variety of testing locations where new applications can be tested in close cooperation with end users. The WaterCampus does not focus on any particular development stage. Innovative ideas on TRLs 1-9 are guided to the market. End-users (in the field of water technology often industries and utilities) are involved in every step of the innovation process through membership of, or partnership with, one of the managing partners: from determining the research program to testing the innovations in various Living Labs. The WaterCampus employs a highly skilled staff and is equipped with high quality research and innovation facilities and, including a set of real-life demo sites to test innovations in. Over the years, the WaterCampus has become a mature Living Lab which involves roughly 300 businesses and knowledge institutions, is active in multiple European programs and has become a household name in the field of water technology.

Areas of work

- Circular Economy
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Urban
- Water (Blue Economy)
- Zero pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

Business
Model
Innovation

Impact
Assessments

Implementation
after Testing

Innovation
Strategies

Scaling-up

Stakeholder
Management

Living Lab
Evaluation

User & Living
Lab Research

Real-life
Experimentation

Living Labs in NORWAY

Accepted to Grow

FATE living lab

Telemark Research
Institute (Stiftelsen
Telemarksforskning)

Country: Norway

www.telemarksforskning.no

The FATE Living Lab in Østfold, Norway, focuses on co-creating and testing interventions that promote sustainable food practices and healthier mindsets among high school students. Embedded in regional policies on organic food and school canteens, it takes a holistic approach linking agriculture, public health, education, and local business development. Through participatory processes, it engages schools, farmers, NGOs, startups, and public bodies, with partners including Nofima, Østfold County Council, and Guldkorn. As part of a larger project, the lab explores how young people can be empowered to engage with sustainable food systems.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Circular Economy
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Regulatory Learning
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Other areas of work

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation

Participatory Tools & Methods

Governance Modelling

Impact Assessments

Policy Making

Stakeholder Management

Living Lab Evaluation

Scaling-up

Panel Management

Real-life Experimentation

User & Living Lab Research

Service Design

Adherent Member

Sustainable Built Environments for Health and Wellbeing (SWELL)

NTNU - Norwegian University of Science and Technology

Country: Norway
www.ntnu.edu

The SWELL – Sustainable Built Environments for Health and Wellbeing Living Lab was originally established as a local arena in Trondheim, Norway, for open and user driven innovation related to mobile services and technology. In the last years, we have focussed on supporting stakeholder engagement using digital technologies. In particular, we focus on enhancing the health and well being of people in the built environment, and exploring digital technologies and diverse methods to support sustainable solutions.

By being a member of ENoLL, we aim to extend and improve the development of services through increased inspirations, ideas and resources by engaging with users, in particular, students and school children, and also participants from other Living Labs.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Health & Well Being
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban

Main Expertise

 Policy Making						
 User & Living Lab Research						

Living Labs in POLAND

Accepted to grow

Campus Living Lab Jagiellonian University **Country: Poland**
<https://www.linkedin.com/company/campus-living-lab/posts/?feedView=all>

Campus Living Lab (CaLiLab) is a university-based living lab operated by Jagiellonian University, which utilizes the campus space as an experimental environment for designing, implementing, and testing innovative solutions. As an open collaboration platform, CaLiLab brings together the academic community, society and both public and private sector stakeholders to co-create knowledge and innovation under real-life conditions. The main areas of CaLiLab’s activity focus on social and business innovations as well as blue-green infrastructure. CaLiLab serves as a catalyst for transforming the campus towards sustainable development, while also providing a research and educational resource for students, doctoral candidates, and academic staff of the Jagiellonian University.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Participatory Tools & Methods	Governance Modelling	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Policy Making
Scaling-up	Stakeholder Management	Living Lab Evaluation	Panel Management	Real-life Experimentation	Service Design	User & Living Lab Research

Effective Member

Krakow Living Lab Krakow Technology Park **Country: Poland**
www.kpt.krakow.pl/en

The Kraków Living Lab is a platform for testing products and services in the conditions in which they are used in life. Tests are conducted in the final/target context of use and operations not only verify the product concept but also point to the potential challenges and unforeseen aspects of use. The process of testing follows a structured iterative plan from concept via prototype to the implementation proper.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Environment/Climate Change
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Mobility
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Participatory Tools & Methods	Governance Modelling	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Policy Making
Scaling-up	Stakeholder Management	Living Lab Evaluation	Panel Management	Real-life Experimentation	Service Design	

Effective Member

PCSS Future Labs

Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center (PSNC)

Country: Poland

www.futurelabs.psnc.pl

PCSS Future Labs Real people - actual problems - digital innovations. PSNC FutureLabs is a Living Laboratory, involving the citizens of Poznań and PSNC regional partners in the design of digital innovations and business models. The Living Lab animates local communities of innovators, entrepreneurs and social activists. With 2000+ sqm of advanced IT labs on six floors, it is a space where cutting-edge technologies support the mission of Wielkopolska region smart specializations. PSNC initiates innovative city projects and secures their financing. It also supports the UN Sustainable Development Goals locally and addresses grand challenges of the Horizon Europe thematic clusters. With support from R&D and business partners, it developed HPC4Poland Digital Innovation Hub.

Areas of Work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Media
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation

Participatory Tools & Methods

Impact Assessments

Implementation after Testing

Innovation Strategies

Scaling-up

Stakeholder Management

Living Lab Evaluation

Panel Management

Real-life Experimentation

Service Design

User & Living Lab Research

Living Labs in PORTUGAL

Adherent Member

GreenLab@Lisbon
- Tapada da Ajuda
Campus the Lisbon
Green Lab

Instituto Superior de
 Agronomia/School of
 Agriculture (Universidade
 de Lisboa)

Country: Portugal
<https://www.isa.ulisboa.pt>

The Instituto Superior de Agronomia (ISA) is a leading academic institution contributing to efficient and sustainable agriculture and forestry, food innovation, bio-circularity of product chains, management of natural resources and territories. It is part of the University of Lisbon, which is the largest and highest-ranked university in Portugal. ISA is situated in the heart of Lisbon, in an academic campus spanning an impressive 100 ha in the heart of the Portuguese capital city.

GreenLivingLab@Lisbon is an integral part of ISA and promotes collaborative projects bringing together researchers, students, private companies, the public sector, and the society at large. It functions as an innovation hub driving progress in smart and sustainable practices. The initiative fosters proactive learning attitudes and embodies a vision that prioritizes open education, research, and knowledge dissemination, towards a sustainable future. In this capacity, GreenLivingLab@Lisbon also accommodates spin-off companies and private enterprises aligned with ISA's overarching mission, becoming a valuable asset for the global innovation community, facilitating user-driven innovation and propelling progress towards a brighter future.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Circular Economy
- Environment/Climate Change
- SME & Start-ups

Main Expertise

Innovation Strategies

Participatory Tools & Methods

Real-life Experimentation

Adherent Member

Montado Living Lab

Universidade de Évora

Country: Portugal

The Montado Living Lab is dedicated to fostering sustainable practices that enhance the diverse functions of the Montado agrosilvopastoral system. Its core focus is on improving soil health, conserving and restoring biodiversity, and ensuring socio-economic balance. This innovation hub brings together a wide range of stakeholders, including farmers, researchers, policymakers, associations, and companies. It acts as a real-world environment where new ideas are experimented with and developed together, following co-construction and transdisciplinary approaches. The Montado Living Lab promotes research and shares knowledge through close collaboration between the scientific community and practical application. Research questions are jointly identified and formulated by multiple partners, with solutions explored by researchers and end users from various disciplinary backgrounds.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Circular Economy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Rural
- Soil
- Water (Blue Economy)
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation

Participatory Tools & Methods

Governance Modelling

Impact Assessments

Implementation after Testing

Innovation Strategies

Policy Making

Scaling-up

Stakeholder Management

Living Lab Evaluation

Real-life Experimentation

Service Design

User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

Smart Rural Living Lab Municipality of Penela

Country: Portugal

<https://www.smartrural.pt/>

The Smart Rural Living Lab (SRLL) aims to generate new methodologies and technologies to approach rural territories weaknesses and strengths, and by these becoming a reference in sustainable rural development, exporting knowledge to other territories, and working with users to foster this specific region. The problems faced by this type of territory, as the Penela Municipality, are primarily focused on improving the local economic base and develop the natural resources, promoting citizenship and entrepreneurship, increasing welfare and social development, tourism promotion and territory identity preservation.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Circular Economy
- Energy
- Rural
- SME & Start-ups

Main Expertise

Innovation
Strategies

Implementation
after Testing

Stakeholder
Management

Living Labs in REPUBLIC OF KOREA

Adherent Member

Daegu Creative Living Lab Daegu Technopark (Digital Transformation Agency) **Country: Republic of Korea**
<https://dgtp.or.kr/eng/>

The Daegu Technopark operates a city innovation platform through Living Lab. It trains citizens to create innovation seeds to participate in Living Labs and trains diverse citizens to become citizen scientists. The organisation helps solve urban problems by operating various Living Labs such as Social Living Lab, Alley Living Lab, and Smart City Living Lab, centring on trained citizen scientists. It also promotes the cultures that change the city through the Living Lab, and ultimately serve as a window for a sustainable city.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation, Participatory Tools & Methods, Governance Modelling, Impact Assessments, Implementation after Testing, Innovation Strategies, Policy Making, Scaling-up, Stakeholder Management, Panel Management, Real-life Experimentation, Service Design, User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

Smart Safety Living Lab Korea Institute of Industrial Technology (KITECH) **Country: Republic of Korea**
<https://ssll.knicc.re.kr/>

Smart Safety Living Lab is an innovative platform that encourages the participation of stakeholders and users to reflect user experiences in the development process of new products and services for SMEs. To support user-participatory innovation activities, the Korea National Industrial Convergence Centre at the Korea Institute of Industrial Technology has established spaces that simulate real product and service usage environments and has built equipment to collect and analyse user and environmental information. In collaboration with specialized institutions, the centre supports activities necessary at each stage of the development, including: business model planning, developing concepts considering market demand and creating business models for successful commercialization; user experience validation, evaluating and verifying usability, safety, and user experience value; certification services, providing consulting for test certifications, test evaluations, and developing standards.

Areas of work

- Health & Well Being
- Media
- SME & Start-ups

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation, Participatory Tools & Methods, Governance Modelling, Policy Making, Scaling-up, Stakeholder Management, Living Lab Evaluation, Panel Management, Real-life Experimentation, Service Design, User & Living Lab Research

Living Labs in ROMANIA

Accepted to Grow

Agrodatasmart

Agricultural Research and Development Station of Braila

Country: Romania

<https://www.scdabraila.ro>

AGRODATASMART LL is coordinated by ARDS Braila (Agricultural Research-Development Station) whose motto is "Research for well-being", together with the AGROSMART Cluster "Together we are better and stronger" an association comprising 15 members (farmers, universities, companies, local authorities).

AGRODATASMART is a Living Lab that aims to develop precision agriculture in Romania. Therefore, the digitization of agriculture is promoted, through the use of sensors, satellite images, weather stations and drones, for the supervision of agricultural and horticultural crops and the timely adoption of phytosanitary treatment measures. The main objective is to reduce as much as possible the use of pesticides and to protect the environment.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Circular Economy
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Research
- Soil

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Participatory Tools & Methods	Governance Modelling	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Scaling-up
Stakeholder Management	Real-life Experimentation	Service Design	User & Living Lab Research			

Adherent Member

Good Tech Lab

Atelierul de Idei Train-IC SRL

Country: Romania

<https://www.atelierul-ideilor.ro>

Good Tech Living Lab is a human-centered innovation space dedicated to advancing ethical, explainable, and inclusive AI solutions through real-world experimentation. At its core, the lab integrates the humanoid robot Pepper with an explainable AI (XAI) system to personalize advanced digital skills training and enhance AI literacy. It addresses TRL3–TRL5 development stages and functions as a testbed for trustworthy AI adoption in Living Lab environments. The unique value proposition lies in combining AI ethics maturity assessment with technology transfer, enabling inclusive access to digital innovation. This fosters adoption of AI not just as a tool, but as a socially responsible enabler of public value, workforce upskilling, and regional resilience.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Gender
- Media
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Innovation Strategies

Implementation after Testing

Business Model Innovation

Stakeholder Management

Real-life Experimentation

Service Design

User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

Innovation Hub Bio Danubius

Asociatia Inter-Bio

Country: Romania

<https://www.agroecology-transect.net/innovation-hubs/bio-danubius-romania/>

We serve as test beds and service providers, creating ecosystems where innovations in areas like the green and digital transition, climate action, circular economy, and smart communities can be co-created, tested, and validated. With a strong focus on digital technologies, we offer infrastructure for testing, validation, and maturity assessments, while supporting startups, SMEs, and clusters through integrated services, expert networks, and EU programs. By involving citizens, researchers, companies, and institutions, we foster inclusive innovation, provide training and access to finance, advocate for better regulations, and guide clients through a comprehensive “client journey” approach.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Media
- Soil
- Water (Blue Economy)
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization
- Other areas of work

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation

Governance Modelling

Impact Assessments

Implementation after Testing

Innovation Strategies

Policy Making

Stakeholder Management

Scaling-up

Real-life Experimentation

Service Design

Adherent Member

**NEXUS BEIA 2050
Living Lab**

Beia Consult
International SRL

Country: Romania
<https://beiaro.eu>

The Nexus BEIA 2050 Living Lab aims to support the implementation of clean technologies for sustainable and resilient growth of agri-food sector based on a more efficient use of energy (renewable/solar/hydrogen) and water management in the Balkan thanks to the contribution of ICT technologies like: AI, Blockchain, cloud, big data, quantum), Telemetry (IIoT, IoMT), data analytics, processing, front/back-end, interfaces.

With an international partnership spanning over, NEXUSLL supports strengthening the technology transfer, cooperation between the 4 major actors of Quadruple Helix model, increasing commercialization opportunities and innovation-driven growth in the region. NEXUS LL offers comprehensive indoor and outdoor facilities as test-bed for food, water and energy solutions, offering a wide range of capabilities.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Energy
- Water (Blue Economy)

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Participatory Tools & Methods	Governance Modelling	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Policy Making
Scaling-up	Stakeholder Management	Living Lab Evaluation	Panel Management	Real-life Experimentation	Service Design	User & Living Lab Research

Accepted to Grow

**Ovidius Aqua Line
Living Lab**

Ovidius Aqua Line S.R.L.

Country: Romania
<https://ovidiusaqualine.ro>

Ovidius Aqua Line Living Lab, located on the Danube River in Borcea, Calarasi County, Romania, is dedicated to advancing sustainable aquaculture, focusing on sturgeon. The facility promotes ecological farming and environmental protection, producing high-quality, environmentally friendly products. It features a state-of-the-art indoor fish farm and processing facility, yielding 25 tons annually of sturgeon, trout, and caviar. The lab utilizes high-end IoT equipment for real-time monitoring and control, a backup power supply, modular design fiberglass ponds, and an in-house production unit of concentrated oxygen. Its living lab methodology emphasizes user-centric innovation through co-creation, demonstration, testing, and evaluation of cutting-edge aquaculture solutions.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Rural
- SME & Start-ups

Adherent Member

Transilvania Living Lab

Asociatia Transilvania IT

Country: Romania
www.transilvaniait.ro

Transilvania Living Lab aims to identify cross-sectorial projects with all stakeholders from the regional innovative ecosystem. Transilvania Living Lab strives to put communities and their needs at the heart of innovation, developing and experimenting with projects and services that involve smart approaches. The goal of Transilvania Living Lab is to empower the users of its services (citizens of the region, private companies, clusters, universities, research institutes, public administration) and integrate them into the innovation process, motivating them to participate, putting the right tools in place to enable a bottomup dialogue, and translating ideas into sustainable commercial products or services. The host organization of Transilvania Living Lab works with a wide range of stakeholders, within a public-private-people partnership, trying to provide solutions and cooperation in areas such as ICT, eHealth, eGovernment, education, space, climate change, Earth Observation, social innovation, smart cities and regions.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Policies
- Research
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Urban
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

Effective Member

UVT Digital & Green Living Lab

West University of Timisoara

Country: Romania
www.uvt.ro/cercetare/

Being a comprehensive University that encompasses both STEAM domains, as well as Social Sciences & Humanities, Culture & Creativity and other associated topics, WUT is the first Romanian University to host a macro-level Living Lab, acknowledged by the European Network of Living Labs starting January 2022. Focusing on meaningful transformation projects that contribute to enhanced community wellbeing, the UVT Digital & Green Living Lab makes use of digital and green tools for transformation projects, benefitting from the education and research human capital & infrastructure.

The Living Lab embodies a collaborative nexus involving representatives from academia, public administration, civil society, including citizens, local action groups/ city districts, and companies based in Timișoara, with a primary emphasis on those SMEs or large companies operating within the designated experimental districts.

Areas of work

- Circular Economy
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Urban
- Water (Blue Economy)
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

Living Labs in **SERBIA**

Adherent Member

BELgrade Urban Living LAB

CEUS Centre for Experiments in Urban Studies

Country: Serbia
www.bellab.rs

AI-powered BELgrade urban living LAB (AI-BELLAB) is a collaborative environment where citizens, planning experts, the public sector, and private companies work together to co-create solutions in response to complex urban and climate-related challenges, e.g. climate change adaptation, disaster risk reduction, and climate resilience, reduction of air and soil pollution, urban biodiversity protection, healthy city promotion, and sustainable urban mobility planning. It was established in 2020 as the first Urban Living Lab in Serbia and the Western Balkans. AI-BELLAB is more than just a testbed platform since it provides experimentation in real-life settings, with AI-supported tools creating equitable and inclusive processes for public urban space co-creation. Amidst rising urbanization and political challenges, intensified by the global ecological and economic crisis, the Living Lab approach provides a new and creative solution for the implementation of public policies and urban design projects.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Circular Economy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Mobility
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation

Participatory Tools & Methods

Governance Modelling

Policy Making

Stakeholder Management

Living Lab Evaluation

Panel Management

Service Design

Real-life Experimentation

User & Living Lab Research

Effective Member

PA4ALL - Precision Agriculture for All

BioSense Institute

Country: Serbia
www.biosens.rs

PA4ALL – Precision Agriculture Living Lab is the first living laboratory in Serbia and one of the first in Europe to focus on precision agriculture. PA4ALL takes full advantage of inter-sectoral cross-fertilization of ideas and offers possibilities to test ideas and prototypes in the real-world setting. PA4ALL based its activities on educating its community on precision agriculture, motivating end-users to test and validate the IT innovations and ensuring their adoption among various stakeholders. PA4ALL activities are bridging the gap between the leisurely changing public sector and modern technologies which are modifying the way agriculture is perceived today. By reinforcing co-creation and multistakeholder participation, PA4ALL is not only gradually widening its network but also encouraging and supporting new Living Labs which emerged in the region in the meantime. In addition to the abovementioned, throughout the Living Lab approach, PA4ALL plans to create a future network of actors who are expected to closely cooperate in the field of agroecology, which is a new concept thriving to become a pivotal change in the way agriculture production impacts then environment.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Circular Economy
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation

Participatory Tools & Methods

Impact Assessments

Implementation after Testing

Policy Making

Stakeholder Management

Living Lab Evaluation

Panel Management

Real-life Experimentation

User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

Pannonia Climate Neutral Agriculture Living Lab

University of Novi Sad,
Faculty of Agriculture

Country: Serbia
agrocampus.rs/

The Pannonian Climate Neutral Agriculture Living lab - PCNA LL epitomizes the definition of being a regional orchestrator of well-coordinated open innovation processes for co-created innovations in real-world settings for climate neutral solutions in agriculture. The PCNA LL's members are the leading actors of the agricultural sector in Vojvodina region on of the part of the Pannonian region. The UNSFA is the largest agricultural faculty in the Western Balkans, while AgroCampus is the largest demo farm in the country. ABE is a regional leading cluster organization in the field of regenerative agriculture with wide dissemination reach. IRI is an economic think tank that covers social science aspects of PCNA LL related to multi-actor engagement, co-creation and open innovation, sustainable business models, impact assessments, and socio-economic analyses. The PCNA LL is a beacon of open innovation allowing companies and researchers to test innovations in a real-life environment.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Circular Economy
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonisation

Main Expertise

Participatory Tools & Methods

Governance Modelling

Impact Assessments

Innovation Strategies

Policy Making

Scaling-up

Stakeholder Management

Living Lab Evaluation

Real-life Experimentation

User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

E-zavod Living Lab

E-zavod

Country: Slovenia

www.ezavod.si

E-zavod living lab focuses on transfer and mainstreaming of open innovation practices to Slovenia.

Work is focused on different areas and is mainly project driven. E-zavod Living Lab focuses on the following thematic sectors: Circular economy, Energy Efficiency and renewable energy, Textile sector, Smart cities, Nature based solutions.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Business
Model
Innovation

Participatory
Tools &
Methods

Governance
Modelling

Implementation
after Testing

Innovation
Strategies

Living Lab
Evaluation

Real-life
Experimentation

Living Labs in SLOVENIA

Effective Member

Green Point F2F Living Lab ITC Murska Sobota

Country: Slovenia
dih-agrifood.com/greenpoint-living-lab/

Green Point Farm to Fork (F2F) Living Lab is a place-based innovation ecosystem based on a Multi-Actor Approach. It involves farmers, food producers, businesses, technology providers, consumers, and local authorities. It brings together diverse actors to co-create and test systemic solutions for sustainable food systems tailored to the specific needs of the Pomurje region.

Its vision is a resilient, sustainable, and locally governed food system in which producers thrive, communities access healthy local food, and sustainability is embedded throughout production, distribution, and consumption.

It focuses on technological (e.g. blockchain, big data, data sharing), economic (circular economy, food loss and waste reduction), and social (consumer participation, local food networks) innovations, implemented and validated in real-life rural settings.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Participatory Tools & Methods	Governance Modelling	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Policy Making
Scaling-up	Stakeholder Management	Living Lab Evaluation	Panel Management	Real-life Experimentation	Service Design	User & Living Lab Research

Living Labs in SPAIN

Adherent Member

Ageing Social Lab

Ageing Social Lab

Country: Spain
www.ageinglab.org

Living Lab Social in real environment offers a comprehensive and direct service providing customized solutions both research projects and in the development as innovation for products and services for the elderly, in order to adapt these products and services to their needs. Living Lab is a real-life test and experimentation environment where users and producers co-create innovations. It seeks a strong user and stakeholder-driven approach and commitment to iterative design, test and validation of solutions. In this sense, the activities of the Living Lab revolve around: i) co-design users, suppliers and designers in developing the concept and definition of the solution; ii) participation and involvement of end users in the process for action research; iii) exploration of ideas and needs for the discovery of new uses or adaptation of resources; iv) the application of live scenarios within the user communities; v) evaluation of concepts, products and services. Living Lab Social in real environment is able to bring together and engage numerous stakeholders in the aging process, by creating synergies through professional, collaborative and expert networks. The development the Living Lab is made with character intergenerational, involving formal and informal caregivers, professionals and institutions in related sectors to improve the quality of life of the aging process (social, health, tourism, knowledge, etc.).

Adherent Member

Alimara Living Lab

CETT Barcelona School of Tourism, Hospitality and Gastronomy

Country: Spain
<https://www.cett.es/en/alimara-living-lab>

Alimara Living Lab (ALL), based in Spain's first university hotel, is an open innovation ecosystem that connects research, education, and the tourism industry. Led by CETT Barcelona School of Tourism, Hospitality and Gastronomy, it provides a real-life space where students, professionals, and stakeholders co-create solutions to hospitality challenges through participatory methods and applied research. With strong governance and cross-sector partnerships, ALL drives operational improvements, scientific advancement, and sustainable transformation while preparing future professionals to tackle complex issues in tourism.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Circular Economy
- Education and/or Vocational Training

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation

Participatory Tools & Methods

Implementation after Testing

Innovation Strategies

Stakeholder Management

Real-life Experimentation

Service Design

Scaling-up

User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

Alimentta Alimentta, Think Tank for the Food Transition **Country: Spain**
alimentta.com

Alimentta was born in 2019 as a Think Tank to accelerate the transition towards sustainable food systems in Spain. Its action is organised around three main streams: 1) the co-production of high-quality scientific knowledge on topics such as the agroecological transition, sustainable fisheries and marine ecosystems, recommendations for a healthy, sustainable diet and participatory governance models 2) stakeholder mobilization and participation in territorial projects based on the Living Lab approach and 3) political incidence actions and initiatives. Alimentta is steered by 10 partners - seasoned researchers in their fields (e.g., agroecology, soil health, marine ecosystems, health), a team of technicians, 29 collaborators and a broader community of practice - farmers, SMEs, retailers, consumer groups, policymakers, etc-. Alimentta's biggest strengths rely on its trans-disciplinary approach to sustainable food transition, its vast network of collaborators and its political influence.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Environment/Climate Change
- Research
- Rural

Main Expertise

Participatory Tools & Methods	Governance Modelling	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Policy Making	Scaling-up
Stakeholder Management	Living Lab Evaluation	Real-life Experimentation	User & Living Lab Research			

Effective Member

BIRD Living Lab GAIA **Country: Spain**
www.birdcenter.org

Bird Living Lab is situated at the Biosphere Reserve of Urdaibai (in the Basque Country, North of Spain) in the Urdaibai Bird Centre. Its mission is to co-create, test, and validate ICT products for environmental management and derivate services and scale them up to new markets, as well as create a community of knowledge in environmental management and smart communities, generating a dynamic launching of innovation and new business structures in this area, allowing an emerging sector in which Europe can be leader. Bird Living Lab focuses on the definition and establishment of a Living Lab approach and methodology to speed and strengthen the projects development, as well as for prototyping of the ideas and products, as well as for final users' involvement in the process. Furthermore, it provides a new way of thinking, not just within the project methodology, but also within the project outcomes and potential, re-thinking about the technology developed, giving new uses, and expanding their potential market to new sectors and countries, generating new business opportunities.

Areas of work

- | | |
|---|---|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Circular Economy • Energy • Environment/Climate Change • Policies • Regulatory Learning | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rural • Smart Cities & Regions • SME & Start-ups • Social Innovation & Inclusion • Zero Pollution & Decarbonization |
|---|---|

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Participatory Tools & Methods	Governance Modelling	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Policy Making
Scaling-up	Stakeholder Management	Living Lab Evaluation	Panel Management	Real-life Experimentation	Service Design	User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

Care & Autonomy Living Lab (CALL) WeMind Cluster

Country: Spain
call.wemindcluster.com/en

Care & Autonomy Living Lab (CALL) is a holistic co-creation space. Its mission is to generate an ecosystem that promotes mental health, neurosciences and ageing through the improvement of the competitiveness of companies and organisations. Innovation, knowledge transfer and collaboration among the different ecosystem agents are fundamental to offer a comprehensive and biopsychosocial support to people.

A realistic approach to healthcare markets through collaborative work, with multidisciplinary and holistic perspectives, is essential for tackling social challenges, promoting also the economic growth of start-ups, SMEs and spin-offs, through an applied technology laboratory.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Health & Well Being
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

Citilab Cornellà

Fundació pel Foment de la Societat del Coneixement

Country: Spain
www.citilab.eu

Citilab is a citizen's laboratory for social and digital innovation, located in Cornellà de Llobregat, Barcelona. It democratizes innovation and develops public policies for citizen social innovation and explores digital impact in creative thinking, design and innovation that emerge from digital culture. Citilab is a mixture between a training centre, a research centre, and a business and social initiative incubator.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Gender
- Health & Well Being
- Media
- Mobility
- Regulatory Learning
- Research
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Effective Member

Colaboratori Catalunya I2CAT Foundation

Country: Spain
www.colabscatalunya.cat

Mission of I2Cat is to transform Catalonia into a collaboratory, a lab of labs. I2Cat will achieve this mission by: i) contributing qualitatively through tangible projects and initiatives to advancing towards a triple social, digital and green inclusive transition in Catalonia; ii) coordinating the variety of knowledges and capacities of quadruple helix stakeholders' collaborative innovations across all the territories in the countries; iii) aligning local and regional needs and defined challenges with European and global agendas and priorities.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Health & Well Being
- Media
- Regulatory Learning
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban

Main Expertise

 Policy Making						
 User & Living Lab Research						

Adherent Member

Food & Health Living Lab

University of Valencia

Country: Spain
www.uv.es/uvweb/food-health-lab

Food&HealthLab is a new research concept focused on users and supported in the open innovation and real scenarios. This initiative includes a series of actions to promote health, healthy and sustainable food strategies, nutritional intervention, and improvement of the quality of life within the branches of the University, at a local, national, and international level. It is aimed, on the one hand, to carry out health interventions in an interdisciplinary environment (with dietitians, nutritionists, food technologists, psychologists, geneticists, experts in preventive medicine, physiotherapist and experts in physical and sport activities), to increase the gastronomic and culinary strategies to adapt menus to individuals and/or patients and developing teams, methods and new tools in health environments, nutrition, gastronomy, physical activity and quality of life with applicability to society.

Areas of work

- | | |
|---|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agriculture & (Agri-)Food • Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR) • Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors) • Education and/or Vocational Training • Environment/Climate Change • Health & Well Being | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industries & Manufacturing • Media • Rural • SME & Start-ups • Social Innovation & Inclusion • Water (Blue Economy) • Zero Pollution & Decarbonization |
|---|--|

Main Expertise

 Policy Making						
 User & Living Lab Research						

Adherent Member

Fundación Épica La Fura dels Baus

Fundación Épica La Fura dels Baus

Country: Spain
www.epicalab.com

Epica has the horizontal collaboration between science, technology, and humanities, as the catalyser for disruptive R+D+I in the new digital era. Thanks to the experience gathered in last 40 years of history of its patrons La Fura dels Baus, Epica has distilled a methodology where, performing arts is the vehicle for these new R+D+I processes, enabling to: i) promote the knowledge transfer between disciplines and to civil society; ii) actively engage into the same ecosystem and processes all quadruple helix agents, through common language; iii) establish the proper sandbox for co-design, experiment, develop, validate, and experience potential future realities and situations (fake realities), new technologies, products and/or processes, through anticipatory arts. Through the use of performing arts, Epica is able to create a neutral environment for cross-research and mutual learning between disciplines and between different players (citizenship, researchers, institutions, companies).

Areas of work

- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Media
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

Galician Network of Health Living Labs

Axencia Galega de Coñecemento en Saúde (ACIS)

Country: Spain
<https://acis.sergas.gal/cartafol/LABSAUDE>

The Galician Network of Health Living Labs, LABSAÚDE, is an initiative fostered by the Galician Health Service (SERGAS) and the Galician Health Knowledge Agency (ACIS) with the purpose of transforming Galician hospitals and health centres into real-life testing hubs for innovative solutions, products or services in the healthcare sector. It aims at establishing an ecosystem of multidisciplinary and multisectorial co-creation, with a focus on the user, by defining an innovative functional model and providing equipment and facilities for different Living Lab scenarios in which health research and innovation studies will be developed.

The Network was first implemented at the University Hospital Complex of Ourense (CHUOU), with a dedicated space for experimental hospitalisation, and has since expanded to the University Hospital Complex of Vigo (CHUVI), where the focus will be on dementia and digital (health) solutions.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Health & Well Being
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

GOe Living Lab

GOe Tech Center

Country: Spain
www.labe-dgl.com

LABe's mission is to drive the digital transformation of gastronomy towards a healthy, sustainable, and delicious future through real context experimentation, innovation and co-creation of digital tools and tech solutions. Main focus areas are: process optimization and automation throughout gastronomy and food supply chain; smart equipment design and development; gastronomy and food experience in the Web 3.0.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Health & Well Being
- SME & Start-ups

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

Healthcare Living Lab Catalonia

ACONDICIONAMIENTO TARRASENSE

Country: Spain
www.healthcarelivinglab.cat

The Healthcare Living Lab Catalonia (HCLLC) is a Living Lab specialized in the health and social fields. Its mission is to bring together healthcare centres, technological centres and Living Labs throughout Catalonia, and connect them to innovation entities and innovative people, facilitating the prototyping, testing and validation of their solutions based on its own methodology and in a fast and efficient way, maximizing the results obtained. The HCLLC offers its services to advise and methodologically guide start-ups, SMEs and companies that want to prototype, test and/or validate innovative solutions in real-life environments and with end users in the fields of medical devices, in vitro diagnostics, and digital health. It is an initiative of Leitat that has the mission of turning Catalonia into a Living Lab of reference and, for this reason, it has a vast network of collaborating entities; on the one hand, the main health centres and innovation referents throughout the country and, on the other hand, the main associations of health and social centres in the country.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Health & Well Being
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

IDEA LIVING LAB

IDEA: INNOVACIÓN Y DESARROLLO ASISTENCIAL

Country: Spain
www.ideainnovacion.com

The Idea Living Lab serves as a central hub in the open health ecosystem, focused on enhancing the quality of life for the elderly. Our work occurs in real environments, aiming to improve without disruption. We research, share knowledge, and create innovative products and services to elevate elderly life. We follow a co-creation, co-design, and person-centered care approach.

Our transdisciplinary technical team, consisting of geriatricians, psychogerontologists, physiotherapists, economists, managers, occupational therapists, social workers, marketing, and business experts, addresses diverse elderly needs across contexts.

Collaboration spans local to European levels, involving universities, elderly associations, research centers, public administrations, and private enterprises. We innovate empathetically, letting the elderly determine the feasibility of innovations based on real needs.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Health & Well Being
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Participatory Tools & Methods	Governance Modelling	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Scaling-up
Stakeholder Management	Living Lab Evaluation	Panel Management	Real-life Experimentation	Service Design	User & Living Lab Research	

Adherent Member

INTERiORS Living Lab

AMBIT LIVING SPACE CLUSTER

Country: Spain
<https://ambitcluster.org/es/>

INTERiORS LIVING LAB by AMBIT Living Spaces Cluster involves in a straightforward manner more than 250 affiliated companies, including home and contract interiors products manufacturers, retailers, and auxiliary industries motivated by innovation from furniture, home textiles, lighting, bath, paving, and other sectors (covering all the interiors value chain). The living lab has a total outreach of more than 2.600 companies across Spain and many other entities across the EU.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Media
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Participatory Tools & Methods	Governance Modelling	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Policy Making
Scaling-up	Stakeholder Management	Living Lab Evaluation	Panel Management	Real-life Experimentation	Service Design	User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

**IoT Smart Santander
Living Lab**

Universidad de
Cantabria

Country: Spain

The IoT SmartSantander Living Lab is aiming at providing an open innovation ecosystem in which companies, research centre and public bodies can undertake new initiatives upon co-creation. Last but not least, citizens leverage on this Living Lab for making a reality the paradigm of data economy.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Circular Economy
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Mobility
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Business
Model
Innovation

Participatory
Tools &
Methods

Governance
Modelling

Impact
Assessments

Implementation
after Testing

Innovation
Strategies

Policy
Making

Scaling-up

Stakeholder
Management

Living Lab
Evaluation

Real-life
Experimentation

Service
Design

User & Living
Lab Research

Adherent Member

**LIVING LAB ECONOMÍA
SOCIAL**

ASATA (AGRUPACIÓN
DE SOCIEDADES
ASTURIANAS DE
TRABAJO ASOCIADO Y
ECONOMÍA SOCIAL)

Country: Spain
asata.es

The LLES Living Lab for Social Economy is focused on social innovation and it is a Living Lab with an innovative approach that involves collaboration among different key agents, in order to design, develop, test, and validate innovative solutions that allow the transformation of long- term care, with the aim of ensuring quality and sustainable care over time.

Areas of work

- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Health & Well Being
- Rural
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban

Adherent Member

Medialab UGR: Research Laboratory for Digital Culture and Society

University of Granada
(Social Innovation
Vicerectorate)

Country: Spain
<https://medialab.ugr.es/>

MediaLab UGR is conceived as a meeting space for the analysis, research and dissemination of the possibilities that digital technologies generate in culture and society in general.

Areas of work

- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Media
- Regulatory Learning
- Rural
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Effective Member

MINDLab

INTRAS Foundation

Country: Spain
www.intras.es

MIND-LAB operates in a quadruple helix innovation ecosystem, focusing on the Castilla y León and Madrid Regions for social-health care, mental health, longevity for vulnerable populations through co-creation, devoted to high-quality research and committed to Open and Responsible Innovation, engaging the public and patients in Participatory and Value-Sensitive Design. Aims to address existing and emerging needs improving social-healthcare services by developing methods and products with researchers, clinicians, technologists, engaging all stakeholders needed. MINDLab focuses in designing, developing, testing: VR/AR for cognitive and multisensory interventions and wellbeing; technologies for neuropsychological assessment, stimulation, rehabilitation, early detection of mild cognitive impairment and to enhance QoL in palliative care; social robotics in care contexts; sensor-enhanced environments to monitor and promote independent living; research in real environments and LL methodologies.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Health & Well Being
- Policies
- Research
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

Neàpolis Neàpolis **Country: Spain**
www.neapolis.cat

An Innovation Agency for technology, communication and creativity, Neàpolis is a Public Innovation Agency for ICT, the multimedia sector, creativity, and entrepreneurship. It offers a space for experimentation, incubation, and growth for the city’s entrepreneurial community, promoting innovation and collaboration. For all of them, coworking and business incubator services are offered as well as connectivity, support, and advice while facilitating its insertion itinerary in the labour market. Since 2006, Vilanova i la Geltrú and its territory of influence have established themselves to promote the innovative ecosystem, ICT businesses, the media, and the creative industries.

Areas of Work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Media
- Mobility
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban
- Other areas of work

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation Participatory Tools & Methods Governance Modelling Impact Assessments Implementation after Testing Innovation Strategies Policy Making

Stakeholder Management Service Design User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

NEUROLAB, ADACEN Living Lab ADACEN, (Navarra Cerebral Damage Association) **Country: Spain**
www.adacen.org

The Adacen Living Lab is an area of research and testing which exists to help patients, designers, researchers and firms to work together on innovations and test products and developments focused on neurological rehabilitation and the promotion of self-sufficiency. Its object is the creation of new services, products and infrastructures that are appropriate for the current needs that the challenge of old age and neurological rehabilitation require.

On being set up and for its subsequent development, the living lab has had its own methodology and has taken on staff that is specialized in neurological rehabilitation and the treatment of the elderly and people with disabilities, who are trained in the processes of innovations centered on the person.

Adacen Living Lab is led by Adacen together with the Public University of Navarra and the Social Innovation Unit of the Government of Navarra and was incorporated in November 2019 to the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL), being the first member of ENoLL in Navarra.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Health & Well Being
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Participatory Tools & Methods Impact Assessments Implementation after Testing Innovation Strategies Scaling-up Stakeholder Management Living Lab Evaluation

Service Design Real-life Experimentation User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

OZEAN LIVING LAB ESKILARA S KOOP TXIKIA **Country: Spain**
www.ozeanlab.tech

Ozean Living Lab is a large-scale open innovation lab to attract companies and promote projects through innovation in strategic sustainable projects. Ozean Living Lab was born to face territorial challenges by promoting the natural environment Urdaibai’s Biosphere Reserve and the competitiveness of the companies in the area through open innovation. A regional strategy with an international perspective: “Improve the quality of life through environmental, social and economic credentials, based on the multifunctional use of Urdaibai’s natural capitals”. Its 4 key objectives are: i) protect ecosystems state and biodiversity; ii) improve ecosystem functioning and promote ecosystem services; iii) promote societal wellbeing and health; iv) support the development of a green economy, and sustainable land and water management.

Areas of work

- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Water (Blue Economy)

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation, Participatory Tools & Methods, Impact Assessments, Implementation after Testing, Innovation Strategies, Policy Making, Scaling-up, Stakeholder Management, Living Lab Evaluation, Real-life Experimentation, Service Design, User & Living Lab Research

Effective Member

Social Digital Lab (Suara) Suara Serveis SCCL **Country: Spain**
www.suara.coop/en

The Social Digital Lab, accredited in 2022 by the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL), is the evolution of the Suara Lab — a new transversal model that transforms the entire organisation and its innovation model toward a new kind of cooperation between public administration, business, citizens, the social economy, and academia.

It is the project that adds value to the innovation process and acts as a lever for the digital transformation of social economy organisations and the creation of services with social impact. It is based on a unique way of understanding and working on innovation, with its own methodological approach, where collaboration with third parties, experimentation, knowledge generation, and the development of digital solutions grounded in reality form the foundation of its activity.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Circular Economy
- Health & Well Being
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation, Participatory Tools & Methods, Governance Modelling, Impact Assessments, Implementation after Testing, Innovation Strategies, Policy Making, Scaling-up, Stakeholder Management, Living Lab Evaluation, Panel Management, Real-life Experimentation, Service Design, User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

Som HEALTH Lab

Parc Sanitari Sant Joan de Déu

Country: Spain
<https://www.pssjd.org/>

The Innovation Unit at Parc Sanitari Sant Joan de Déu (PSSJD) applies a Living Lab methodology to co-create solutions that respond to real needs in healthcare and mental health. Since 2022, it has fostered collaboration among patients, professionals, and key stakeholders through user-centered, iterative innovation processes rooted in community engagement.

Adherent Member

SSI Living Lab

Servicios Sociales Integrados, S. Coop.

Country: Spain
www.grupossi.es

Servicios Sociales Integrados, S. Coop. (Grupo SSI) is a cooperative company set up in Bilbao in 1986, to respond to the social needs of people in situations of dependence and social vulnerability, and their families, in Euskadi. S.S.I. The Group and the entities that belong to it (Aurrerantz, S. Coop. de Iniciativa Social, Aurrerantz Asociación, Euskarri, S. Coop. Empresa de Inserción and Home Care Lab, S. Coop.) promoted the creation of the Living Lab to enrich and strengthen the innovation capacities of the Group around ageing and dependence and improve its competitiveness. Specifically, Home Care Lab, S. Coop., the Group's R&D&I business unit, is one of the most important actors that make up the Living Lab. Home Care Lab, S. Coop. is boosted by the Living Lab, experimenting, and carrying out drills of the daily activities dependent people, the carers, and their families face. The Living Lab is a pioneering infrastructure in Euskadi that attempts to simulate the different rooms of a home with advanced technology. It has 100 sqm and adapted beds and baths, a hydraulic motor cranes, a modular kitchen, etc., resources that are equipped with technological advances that make it easier to care for elderly dependent people.

Areas of work

- Health & Well Being
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation

Participatory Tools & Methods

Impact Assessments

Innovation Strategies

Policy Making

Scaling-up

Panel Management

Real-life Experimentation

Adherent Member

**Sustainable
Desalination Living Lab**

CIEMAT (Centre for Energy, Environment and Technology Research)

Country: Spain

The Sustainable Desalination Living Lab works to enhance the water-energy-food nexus by developing decarbonized desalination solutions and circular economy approaches, including brine valorisation for critical materials. Bringing together CIEMAT, CIESOL, local authorities, farmers, and municipalities, it provides real-life testing environments for academic and industrial innovations. Through a Community of Practice with diverse regional stakeholders, the lab pilots technologies and promotes collaboration, aiming for sustainable water management and certification benefits for agriculture and tourism. It is featured in the Water4All Atlas of water-oriented Living Labs.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Circular Economy
- Energy
- Water (Blue Economy)

Main Expertise

 Living Lab Evaluation						
 User & Living Lab Research						

Adherent Member

**UAB Smart Campus
Living Lab**

University Autònoma of Barcelona

Country: Spain
<https://www.uab.cat/>

The campus has become a primary area for experimentation, innovation and demonstration of new technologies and methodologies, and also an incubator/accelerator for different types of projects and initiatives, which can then be applied in the neighboring municipalities.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban
- Water (Blue Economy)
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

 Policy Making						
 User & Living Lab Research						

**VALENCIA LIVING LAB - PEOPLE
INNOVATING FOR PEOPLE**

Adherent Member

**Valencia Living Lab -
People Innovating for
People**

Fundación de la
Comunidad Valenciana
para la Promoción
Estratégica, el Desarrollo
y la Innovación

Country: Spain
www.lasnaves.com

The aim of this LL is to make Valencia a laboratory city by creating experimentation spaces, public infrastructures and processes designed to experiment with new solutions, services and products that are developed by innovative ecosystem, as well as by the citizenship, and which require testing in real conditions. Within its scope, Valenica LL has been working for years in the development of this experimentative city vision, to which it is now possible to contribute with the following three concrete assets. 1) Las NAVES + La HARINERA Living Lab: the conversion of the public innovation centre in Valencia into a living lab focused on co-creating innovation that improves people’s lives. 2) URBAN REGULATORY SANDBOX of the city of Valencia, which is one of the first local-scale regulatory sandboxes to be created in Spain. 3) TEF – TESTING & EXPERIMENTATION FACILITY, which will be one of the three laboratories to be set up in Europe, in this case focusing on AI.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Mobility
- Policies
- Regulatory Learning
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Soil
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

 Policy Making						
 User & Living Lab Research						

**Living Labs in
SWEDEN**

Adherent Member

Botnia Living Lab

Luleå University of
Technology

Country: Sweden
www.ltu.se

Botnia Living Lab (hosted by LTU) is a member of the European Network of Living Labs (www.enoll.org) and was one of the founders of the network. Botnia Living Lab has matured from a test bed to become a real-life living laboratory in 2006. Botnia is a world-leading environment for user-centric research, development and innovation (RDI), supported by innovative methods, tools and experts.

Areas of work

- Circular Economy
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

HSB Living Lab

HSB Göteborg

Country: Sweden
<https://www.hsb.se/hsblivinglab/>

HSB Living Lab is a journey towards future housing. The project tests completely new technological and architectural innovations over a period of 10 years. The building, located at Chalmers Campus Johanneberg in Gothenburg, is so much more than a house – it is a Living Laboratory where research can be done in a way never done before. HSB Living Lab is a movable four-storey building and was ready for occupancy on June 1, 2016. Three of the floors are housing for students and visiting researchers and on the ground floor there are collaboration rooms with offices, conference rooms, showrooms for research projects, and a modern laundry studio. The accommodation in HSB Living Lab today consists of 29 apartments where tenants live in an ever-changing and evaluated environment, all while the research is ongoing. HSB Living Lab is run by 12 partners to create a solid collaboration arena for new knowledge with a focus on social, economic, and environmental sustainability.

Areas of work

- Circular Economy
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Wellbeing
- Mobility
- Research
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Urban
- Water (Blue Economy)
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonisation

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

Living Lab at Mälardalen University Mälardalen University **Country: Sweden**

The projects managed by MDU Living Lab strives to create an awareness of the co-creation process as such, in developing education programs, courses or research and students' project. MDU Living Lab aims to further develop and document new methods for co-creation within academic education and research.

Areas of work

- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Participatory Tools & Methods Impact Assessments Implementation after Testing Innovation Strategies Stakeholder Management Living Lab Evaluation Panel Management

User & Living Lab Research Real-life Experimentation

Adherent Member

Småland Regional Living Lab Department of Design, Linnaeus University **Country: Sweden**
www.lnu.se/en

Småland Living Lab is about finding and building on synergies between social, cultural, economic, and ecological dimensions of sustainability. Through it experimentation, learning and change, education and inspiration happen simultaneously. The vision of Småland Living Lab is that it will connect a range of initiatives in the remit of sustainability within the region, for knowledge exchange, power, visibility, and also create models for other regions. Småland Living Lab works at the local and regional level to support adaption to a circular economy, and to meet and exceed the UN Sustainable Development Goals. Småland Living Lab uses meta design approaches and tools developed to prompt synergy in transdisciplinary collaborations.

Areas of work

- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Environment/Climate Change
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation Participatory Tools & Methods Governance Modelling Impact Assessments Implementation after Testing Innovation Strategies Scaling-up

Living Lab Evaluation User & Living Lab Research

THE SWEDISH LIVING LAB ON
VEHICLE AND TRANSPORT ICT

Adherent Member

**The Swedish Living
Lab on Vehicle and
Transport ICT**

Country: Sweden

The Swedish Living Lab on Vehicle and Transport ICT (SVT-LL) is a competitive Living Lab for user-driven development of automotive and transport applications and services. The objective of the SVT-LL is to leverage Sweden's strong cluster of automotive and transport firms through the development, adoption, and use of co-creation approaches to product and service innovation. SVT-LL is coordinated by the Viktoria Institute.

Living Labs in
SWITZERLAND

Adherent Member

Ecopol Living Lab & ecovillages Romandie

APTES - Association pour la Promotion de la Transdisciplinarité et de l'Entrepreneuriat social

Country: Switzerland
www.ecopol.net/enoll

Since 1993, the R&D team develops and facilitates ecovillage intergenerational and intercultural dialogue to incubate intentional communities dedicated to deep ecology and energetical sobriety. The Living Lab manages 3 eco-centres gathering families, artists, social entrepreneurs, seniors, refugees, academic researchers, and public officers.

Areas of work

- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Participatory Tools & Methods	Governance Modelling	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Scaling-up
Stakeholder Management	Panel Management	Real-life Experimentation	Service Design	User & Living Lab Research		

Effective Member

Energy Living Lab

HES-SO Valais-Wallis

Country: Switzerland
www.energylivinglab.com

Co-designing an energy decarbonized and desirable future with the help of collective intelligence through on-site interventions. The HES-SO research team works on applied research, methods and tools to further develop the knowledge on applying Living Lab methods in the energy field. Designing research projects, publishing scientific articles, developing a network of researchers, teaching living labs, open innovation and social innovation are our main activities within the Energy Living Lab @HES-SO.

Areas of work

- Circular Economy
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Mobility
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Urban
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Participatory Tools & Methods	Governance Modelling	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Policy Making
Scaling-up	Stakeholder Management	Living Lab Evaluation	Panel Management	Real-life Experimentation	Service Design	User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

FiBL on-farm Network Research Institute of Organic Agriculture **Country: Switzerland**
www.fibl.org

The Living Lab is part of the project ROADMAP (Rethinking of Antimicrobial Decision-Systems in the Management of Animal Production) which will foster transitions towards prudent antimicrobial use (AMU) in animal production in a large variety of contexts, by favouring a rethinking antimicrobial decision system all along the food supply chain.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Environment/Climate Change

Main Expertise

 Policy Making						
 User & Living Lab Research						

Adherent Member

Genève Lab State of Geneva **Country: Switzerland**
www.ge.ch/dossier/geneve-lab

Genève Lab supports the public administration of the State of Geneva in the transformation induced by the challenges of the digital age. This consists of helping project leaders to adopt a user-centred approach, to work in a collaborative, multidisciplinary manner and by opening up to our ecosystem, as well as to favour prototyping and iteration.

Areas of work

- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Other areas of work

Main Expertise

 Panel Management						
 User & Living Lab Research						

Adherent Member

iHomeLab (iHL) Hochschule Luzern Technik & Architektur **Country: Switzerland**
www.ihomelab.ch

The iHomeLab Living Lab of the Lucerne University of Applied Sciences (LUAS) is the leading research centre for building intelligence in Switzerland. Connected within a broad network of experts, it also engages in international initiatives to further develop these fields, contributes to scientific conferences and trade fairs and actively takes part in shaping new standards and technologies being a member of several technology standards organisations and professional unions (e.g. ZigBee Alliance, KNX Scientific, IEEE, IPv6 Swiss Council, AALOA, 4E, terzStiftung). Together with its industrial partners, the iHomeLab Living Lab team conducts applied research to increase the energy efficiency, security and comfort in residential as well as commercial buildings. The research strategy focuses on the three research areas of energy efficiency (EE), ambient assisted living (AAL) and human building interaction (HBI) under the roof of the meta-research topic “The Building as a System” at the Lucerne University of Applied Sciences.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Energy
- Health & Well Being
- Research
- Smart Cities & Regions

Main Expertise

Innovation Strategies, Stakeholder Management, Living Lab Evaluation, Real-life Experimentation, Business Model Innovation, Service Design, User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

Living Lab for Special Needs HES-SO Valais-Wallis **Country: Switzerland**
<https://frh-fondation.ch/en/>

Founded in 2018, in collaboration with the HES-SO Valais-Wallis, the Living Lab for Special Needs aims to create an innovation platform for disability in the broadest sense. It acts as a forum to exchange between different partners on disability-related issues, with the aim of developing new technological solutions and/or services that can help them. It is a co-creation and innovation network, a space to exchange bringing together people with disabilities, scientists, companies and all other people interested in collaborating in the field of disability and in the co-creation of new innovative solutions. Living Lab Handicap is accredited by the European Network of Living Labs.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Health & Well Being
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Other areas of work

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation, Participatory Tools & Methods, Governance Modelling, Impact Assessments, Implementation after Testing, Innovation Strategies, Policy Making, Scaling-up, Stakeholder Management, Living Lab Evaluation, Panel Management, Real-life Experimentation, Service Design, User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

Lugano Living Lab City of Lugano **Country: Switzerland**
<https://www.luganolivinglab.ch/>

The need for a modern quality management of public affairs, based on data, facts and figures and functional for the vision and strategy defined by the Municipality, has led to the creation of the Lugano Living Lab operating platform, as a concrete response aimed at encouraging innovation to further improve the quality of life of citizens and the attractiveness of the region.

Areas of work

- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Health & Well Being
- Mobility
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation Participatory Tools & Methods Governance Modelling Impact Assessments Implementation after Testing Innovation Strategies Policy Making

Scaling-up Stakeholder Management Living Lab Evaluation Panel Management Real-life Experimentation Service Design User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

mQoL Living Lab: Mobile Communications and Computing for Life Quality University of Geneva **Country: Switzerland**
mqol.unige.ch

Our goal is to measure quality of life as it naturally unfolds—across time, place, and context. We treat everyday behavior as something that can be observed, analyzed, and improved—much like a cardiologist examines a heart. Our research covers healthy aging, migraines, diabetes, obesity, joint recovery, and breast cancer, focusing on outcomes that matter to patients, not just clinical results. We’ve received over 45 research grants and published nearly 200 peer-reviewed papers. Our work helps improve how we assess disease risk and treatment effects. Through our mQoL Living Lab and software platform, we co-design and test new health apps using real-time data, machine learning, and cutting-edge AI—advancing personalized, practical solutions in digital healthcare.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Gender
- Health & Well Being
- Mobility
- Research
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Soil
- Urban
- Water
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization
- Other areas of work

Main Expertise

Participatory Tools & Methods Implementation after Testing Innovation Strategies Policy Making Scaling-up Stakeholder Management Living Lab Evaluation

Panel Management Real-life Experimentation Service Design User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

Mobility Lab CH

Swiss Post Ltd,
Corporate Development,
CEO Corporate Services

Country: Switzerland
www.mobilitylab.ch

The challenges in the public space, particularly in the area of transport and mobility, will increase in the coming years. The Mobility Lab wants to provide innovative solutions. Since 2014, the Mobility Lab in Sion-Valais has brought together the Federal Institute of Technology Lausanne (EPFL), the University of Applied Sciences HES-SO Valais-Wallis, the Canton of Valais, the City of Sion and Swiss Post. Together, these partners develop innovative ideas and test solutions in the public space in Sion and its region, particularly in the field of mobility.

Areas of work

- Circular Economy
- Energy
- Mobility
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Urban
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

Participatory Tools & Methods

Impact Assessments

Implementation after Testing

Innovation Strategies

Stakeholder Management

Real-life Experimentation

Service Design

User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

Senior-Lab

Institut et Haute Ecole
de la Santé La Source;
HEIG-VD; ECAL (HES-SO)

Country: Switzerland
www.senior-lab.ch

The senior-lab is an innovation and research platform dedicated to the quality of life of the elderly. The interdisciplinary approach is in its DNA as it was created by three schools of applied sciences, each one specialized in very different, but complementary, subjects (management, engineering, health, art, and design). The Living Lab team strongly believes that no successful innovation is possible without the involvement of the end-users already from the first steps of the process. For this reason, it develops all projects with a community of senior citizens, in a user-driven mindset. The elderly share their experiences, expectations, and aspirations to co-create products, services and technologies that will concretely match their needs.

Areas of work

- Health & Well Being
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Participatory Tools & Methods

Impact Assessments

Implementation after Testing

Stakeholder Management

Living Lab Evaluation

Panel Management

Service Design

User & Living Lab Research

Real-life Experimentation

Adherent Member

Smart Living Lab

EPFL (Ecole polytechnique fédérale de Lausanne, Switzerland)

Country: Switzerland
www.smartlivinglab.ch

The Smart Living Lab is a research and development centre for the future of the built environment. It focuses on carbon footprint, energy systems, construction technology, digital transformation, comfort, and well-being of users (IEQ, user-building interactions). Interdisciplinary research projects are pursued with experiments carried out in real-life conditions.

Areas of work

- Circular Economy
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Water (Blue economy)
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

Impact Assessments, Participatory Tools & Methods, Implementation after Testing, Scaling-up, Stakeholder Management, Real-life Experimentation, User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

Swiss Food Research

Swiss Food Research

Country: Switzerland
www.swissfoodresearch.ch/de/

Swiss Food Research (SFR) is Switzerland’s largest Agro-Food and Nutrition Innovation Network. Together with its 200+ members from academia, industry, and society, SFR catalyses holistic innovation along the entire value chain to support transformation toward a future-oriented agro food & nutrition system. Swiss Food Research supports projects from the problem up to market readiness in a neutral, confidential, and independent manner. This support ranges from knowledge transfer, sparring, workshops, to funding support, to market testing within real warm data environment.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Circular Economy
- SME & Start-ups

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation, Participatory Tools & Methods, Governance Modelling, Impact Assessments, Implementation after Testing, Innovation Strategies, Policy Making, Scaling-up, Stakeholder Management, Living Lab Evaluation, Panel Management, Real-life Experimentation, Service Design, User & Living Lab Research

Accepted to grow

Urban Living Lab (OUF) Open Urbanism Foundation

Country: Switzerland
<https://openurbanism.ch/en>

Since 2010, our Urban Living Lab has been pioneering free and open-source methods and tools that prioritize citizen and urban user engagement in city transformation processes. Our approach seeks to foster a dialogue between professionals and civil society. We believe this is essential for achieving transformative changes and building new trust towards sustainable lifestyles through co-construction. Our efforts have been recognized with several awards, including the European Commission's Open Cities prize for our Unlimited Cities visual and textual intelligence tool. The tool's international reach was significantly boosted when it was selected as a good practice by the UN-Habitat agency at the Habitat III conference in Quito in 2016. Since then, Unlimited Cities has been utilized in regions such as China, South America, Africa, and Europe.

Living Labs in **TAIWAN**

Effective Member

Taiwan Living Lab

Institute for Information Industry

Country: Taiwan

www.livinglabs.com.tw/en/

The Taiwan Living Lab operated by Institute for Information Industry is committed to three core values: innovation, compassion, and effectiveness. Institute for Information Industry will follow a well-designed blueprint of services to choose the target group to serve and design various experiments to evaluate the performances of new technological services. Its mission is to assist domestic businesses to proceed the PoC, PoS and PoB projects in the validation phase of service concept to reduce the potential risks for lacking proper understanding of the market, and to raise the chance to succeed in IT enabled service providing businesses.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Mobility
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation

Participatory Tools & Methods

Governance Modelling

Impact Assessments

Implementation after Testing

Innovation Strategies

Policy Making

Scaling-up

Stakeholder Management

Living Lab Evaluation

Panel Management

Real-life Experimentation

Service Design

User & Living Lab Research

Living Labs in TUNISIA

Adherent Member

DigiArt Living Lab

NetInfo School of art and technology

Country: Tunisia
www.dall4all.org

Digiart Living Lab (DALL) is a creative platform for social and open innovation. The DALL is a space to welcome the African talents wishing to develop their creative spirit and wanting to produce creative, innovative projects, having a social impact, and using creative and digital technologies (3D, Video game, Virtual Reality, Augmented Reality, IoT, etc.). DALL's main mission is to support the community of young people and talents passionate about creative and digital technologies, to organize events and to carry out projects that contribute to the development of the digital arts sector in African Continent.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Media
- Policies
- Regulatory Learning
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban

Main Expertise

Impact Assessments

Participatory Tools & Methods

Implementation after Testing

Stakeholder Management

Real-life Experimentation

User & Living Lab Research

Service Design

Adherent Member

Sidi Amor Water Living Lab (WLL)

Hanns Seidel Foundation (HSF)

Country: Tunisia
<https://sidiamor.org/>

The Sidi Amor Water Living Lab (WLL) is a community-led initiative addressing acute water scarcity in one of the world's most water-stressed regions. The lab engages rural women, youth (including NEETs), and farmers in co-developing innovative solutions for wastewater treatment, sustainable agriculture, and ecosystem restoration. It serves as a practical model for climate adaptation, biodiversity recovery, and water reuse in the Global South.

Living Labs in TURKEY

Effective Member

BAŞAKŞEHİR LIVING LAB

Başakşehir Municipality

Country: Turkey

www.basaksehirlivinglab.com

Başakşehir Living Lab is certificated as Turkey's first Living Lab in May 2012. Başakşehir Living Lab is established for spreading innovation and entrepreneurship based on ICT and industrial design, supporting the new business opportunities, developing new easily accessible services for Başakşehir citizens, and promoting the awareness of citizens to new technological improvements. Başakşehir Living Lab serves at Başakşehir Municipality Innovation and Technology Center, located in Başakşehir District of Istanbul, where it is equipped with the latest technology and is the first public sector building that has LEED Gold Certification. In total, it has 3,000 sqm indoor space and many specialized areas in it, such as user experience centre, electronic lab, 3D modelling and printing area, incubation area, design factory, conference room, workshop hall and social area.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Media
- Mobility
- Policies
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban
- Water (Blue Economy)
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

Bodrum Living Lab

Keyifli İşler A.Ş

Country: Turkey

www.bodrumlivinglab.com

Bodrum Living Lab (BoLL) is an enabling co-creation hub where innovative products and services are developed in real life environments and with real users, coordinating all stakeholders of a start-up or a project (public, private sector, universities, and local citizens). BoLL aspires to play a key role in bringing all stakeholders of Bodrum to co-innovate and bring value creating projects into life. It focuses on Bodrum's key economic activities: maritime, tourism, agriculture, and wellness. The Living Lab invites all innovators to join and create value for Bodrum.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Health & Well Being
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Other areas of work
- Tourism

Main Expertise

Innovation Strategies

Stakeholder Management

Impact Assessments

Business Model Innovation

Real-life Experimentation

Adherent Member

Mezopotamya Living Lab

Şanlıurfa Metropolitan Municipality

Country: Turkey

www.mezopotamyall.com

Mezopotamya Living Lab's goal is to raise the living standards of the residents and to move beyond the standards offered by the Şanlıurfa metropolitan municipality. It does so by using technology accordingly and consciously in every aspect of life in coordination with the non-governmental organizations of the region, cooperatives of farmers and Professional chambers. The Living Lab provides value to different spheres of the economy. With ECOTECHNOLOGY AGRICULTURE and RENEWABLE ENERGY, it develops the land with technology and aims to benefit from natural energy. With SMART TOURISM and CULTURE, it seeks to see the actual value of technology in world tourism with all the possibilities at zero point in history. With INFORMATICS, ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE and INNOVATION, it works continuously with current trainings and mentor support to ensure that ideas and initiatives have a say in the world market.

Areas of work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Media
- Policies
- Regulatory Learning
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban
- Water (Blue Economy)

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation

Participatory Tools & Methods

Governance Modelling

Impact Assessments

Implementation after Testing

Innovation Strategies

Policy Making

Scaling-up

Stakeholder Management

Living Lab Evaluation

Panel Management

Real-life Experimentation

Service Design

User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

**Samsun Coastal City
Living Lab**

Samsun University

Country: Turkey

<https://meteoroloji.samsun.edu.tr/samsun-coastal-city-living-lab/>

The Samsun Coastal City Living Lab (Samsun CCLL) is a climate resilience-focused Living Lab established within the EU-funded SCORE project. Embedded in a multidisciplinary academic environment, the lab fosters co-creation, citizen engagement, and real-life experimentation to address environmental challenges in coastal urban areas. With an emphasis on nature-based solutions, participatory climate adaptation, and citizen science, Samsun CCLL develops locally tailored approaches to issues such as sea-level rise, coastal erosion, and salinization.

Areas of work

- Environment/Climate Change
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Urban
- Water (Blue Economy)
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation

Participatory Tools & Methods

Governance Modelling

Impact Assessments

Implementation after Testing

Innovation Strategies

Policy Making

Scaling-up

Stakeholder Management

Living Lab Evaluation

Panel Management

Real-life Experimentation

User & Living Lab Research

Living Labs in **UNITED KINGDOM**

Effective Member

Bristol Living Lab

Knowle West Media Centre

Country: United Kingdom

kwmc.org.uk

The mission of the Living Lab is “Making fair and thriving neighbourhoods with art, tech & care”. Bristol Living Lab is run by Knowle West Media Centre (KWMC), a UK based non-profit arts organisation with 20 years’ experience of working with communities and individuals to understand how creativity and digital technologies can be utilised to meet local needs and address system change. It is a community based ‘enabler- driven’ Living Lab: KWMC acts as a ‘broker’ between citizens and organisations, ensuring that each participant in a particular project is able to contribute their knowledge and experience. KWMC adopts an ‘action research’ approach, where continual reflection and evaluation are built into the working process, and this enables KWMC to be flexible and responsive to the changing needs of partners and communities. It has a wide range of citywide, regional, and international networks that it actively works with and takes a ‘Commons’ Approach to sharing knowledge and learning.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Culture & Creativity (Creative Sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban

Main Expertise

Participatory Tools & Methods Governance Modelling Implementation after Testing Innovation Strategies Policy Making Stakeholder Management

Service Design User & Living Lab Research

Effective Member

City Lab Coventry

Coventry University

Country: United Kingdom

City Lab Coventry is an urban research-driven living lab drawing on the expertise and networks of staff from across Coventry University, providing an open environment for participatory research projects and initiatives. Particular areas of interest and expertise include circular economy, education and training, health and wellbeing, mobility, smart cities and urban areas, and social innovation and inclusion. We aim to work with and bring together a diverse range of local, national, and international partners and stakeholders, including SMEs, local communities, NGOs, charitable organizations, governmental departments, universities, and research organizations, to generate co-created, multi-disciplinary research-based knowledge and deliver outcomes with international significance.

Areas of work

- Circular Economy
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Health & Well Being
- Mobility
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban

Main Expertise

Participatory Tools & Methods Impact Assessments Implementation after Testing Policy Making Stakeholder Management Living Lab Evaluation Panel Management

User & Living Lab Research Real-life Experimentation

Effective Member

Digital Health and Care Innovation Centre and Moray Rural Centre of Excellence and StrathLab

University of Strathclyde

Country: United Kingdom

www.dhi-scotland.com

DHI is one of Scotland's 4 active Innovation Centres devoted to new digital technologies for health and care of citizens. Its mission is to enhance the populations longevity and health stimulating the economy, collaborating, co-designing and transforming innovative ideas into solutions by providing engagement, facilitation, project management, services, business and technical innovation using Living Lab Methodology. Funded by the UK Government, DHI leads the Rural Centre of Excellence for Digital Health and Care Innovation in the Moray Region (RCE) aimed at mobilising health and care services. The RCE identified 5 areas explored via Living Labs, supported by a Citizen Panel and underpinned by a virtual R&D infrastructure: supported self-management – working with industry and public sector partners to innovate a digitally integrated solution to support weight management and active; long term conditions co-management; care in place; smart housing/smart communities; mental wellbeing.

Areas of work

- Emerging Technologies (e.g. AI, AR/VR)
- Health & Well Being
- Research
- Rural
- Soil

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

Innovate Dementia Transnational Living Lab

Liverpool John Moores University

Country: United Kingdom

<https://www.ljmu.ac.uk/>

The Innovate Dementia Transnational Living Lab hosted by the Centre for Collaborative Innovation in Dementia at Liverpool John Moores University is a research-to-innovation asset. The Lab arose out of the successes of the Innovate Dementia project. The central aim of the project was to engage with people living with dementia to develop innovative ways of addressing their everyday challenges. The project team worked with people living with dementia, the business sector – SMEs and multinational companies, other academics, and commissioners and providers of services. Transnationally over 15 innovations were brought to the market. The work of the project was based on a robust participatory engagement process, in 2014 the Centre's Living Lab was accredited by ENOLL. The Lab has widened its reach by working with co-creation groups across health and social care, this work is not always condition specific, it can be international, however, it is always grounded within the needs of the most vulnerable in society.

Areas of work

- Health & Well Being
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

Lab4Living

Sheffield Hallam University

Country: United Kingdom

www.lab4living.org.uk

Lab4Living is a trans-disciplinary research group, based on a collaborative community of researchers in design, healthcare, and creative practices. These work together to address real world issues that impact on health and wellbeing, developing products, services and interventions that promote dignity and enhance quality of life.

Areas of work

- Health & Well Being

Main Expertise

 Panel Management						
 Real-life Experimentation						

**European
Network of
Living Labs**

